

Master Thesis

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Utilizing Artificial Intelligence to Reduce the Impact of Climate Change on Wildlife

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“Nature has always looked like a horrible mess, but as we go along we see patterns and put theories together; a certain clarity comes and things get simpler.”

— Professor Richard P. Feynman (1918–1988), *QED* (1990, p. 149).

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Abstract

Current anthropogenic climate change poses a significant threat to biodiversity, rapidly driving species towards extinction. Wildlife conservation relies on the speed and accuracy of processing environmental data, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a promising tool to assist wildlife conservation efforts. This thesis conducts a literature review to explore how artificial intelligence is being utilized to mitigate the impacts of climate change on wildlife. It examines the key applications of artificial intelligence, such as monitoring wildlife, predicting species distribution under climate effects, mitigation solutions, and poaching and trafficking detection. This literature review focuses on identifying the effective artificial intelligence models in current conservation practices, highlighting their capabilities, challenges, and limitations. The findings suggest that artificial intelligence can significantly enhance wildlife monitoring and conservation planning, as well as providing tools to predict environmental changes and plan mitigation strategies. However, certain challenges including technical limitations, ethical considerations, and data availability remain obstacles to utilizing the full potential of artificial intelligence in this field. Future research should focus on the development of unified species databases, identifying the most reliable models, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), and cost-effective solutions, while addressing ethical issues. This thesis concludes that artificial intelligence offers valuable opportunities for mitigating the impacts of climate change on wildlife with careful consideration of its limitations and ethical implications.

Keywords: Climate Change, Wildlife Conservation, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Artificial Intelligence Ethics, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)

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1. Introduction

1.1. A Travel in Time

Scientific studies and discoveries verify that through the geological and biological history of the earth, the environment on this planet has been changing. These changes have happened over millions of years and created different geological periods with their specific biodiversity. During each period, the transformations were gradual and resulted in extinction of some species, which biologists consider them as normal rates of extinction (Barnosky et al., 2011). However, studies confirm that in the history of our planet there have been dramatic natural phenomena that caused *Mass Extinctions* of species on earth. Mass extinction occurs when more than 75% of species on Earth is lost in a short period of time (Barnosky et al., 2011). Scientists believe five mass extinctions happened during the past 450 million years and each exterminated a significant part of life on Earth (Barnosky et al., 2011; McCallum, 2015).

Table 1. Mass Extinction Events by Date, Potential Causes, and Severity.

Event	Approx. Time million years ago (mya)	Possible Causes	Species Extinction Severity
Ordovician-Silurian	444	Glaciation, lowered sea levels	86%
Late Devonian	359	Changes in sea level, asteroid impacts, climate change	75%
Permian-Triassic	251	Volcanic eruptions, methane release, depletion of seas	96%
Triassic-Jurassic	200	Volcanic activity, climate change, ocean acidification	80%
Cretaceous-Paleogene	66	Asteroid impact, volcanic activity	76%

Source: Author's creation. Data from Barnosky et al. (2011) and McCallum (2015).

While these mass extinctions were caused by natural phenomena, scientists discovered evidence of a less severe extinction around 0.01 million years ago during the *Quaternary* period, in which 55% of large mammals became extinct. In this event, along with climate change, early humans played a significant role by hunting animals (Sandom et al., 2014). Although by the concept of mass extinction this event may not have the same level of significance, when the role of humans is considered, it is the earliest destruction of nature by humans. Nevertheless, some may view it as the act of a new species in the natural food chain that had more advanced hunting equipment.

As humans evolved during that period, in addition to hunting, they learned how to use natural elements to plant their food and build shelters. Although the population of humans was limited, the impact of their

actions is believed to be the early disruption of natural habitat of other species by inventing agriculture (Ceballos et al., 2020). Researchers believe that these evolutions in human behavior have started the Sixth mass biodiversity extinction, entirely caused by humans.

While the beginning of this event dates back thousands of years, biologists who have examined this evidence believe this event has progressed since A.D. 1500 with a larger magnitude (Barnosky et al., 2011; McCallum, 2015; Ceballos et al., 2020; Cowie et al., 2022). This extinction has occurred due to an increase in human population that resulted in extended distribution of humans on Earth. This expansion necessitated the use of natural resources, including destruction of land by farming and building homes. When there were not enough resources, humans relocated to or colonized new areas and extended the disturbance of biodiversity to a larger group of species.

In 2022, Cowie et al. reported that since 1500, which is considered as the cut-off date for tracking current period of extinction, between 7.5 to 13 percent of known species have become extinct. With the start of the *Industrial Revolution* in the 1700s, the destruction of resources took a new form. Humans were not only over-using the resources, but also started to poison the environment with various forms of toxic waste from the factories. The *Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)* report in 2023 shows that since 1750, the increases in CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O are equal to the natural changes in the period of past 800,000 years. This increase in *Greenhouse Gases (GHG)* has created human-caused global warming, which in addition to the extensive use of natural resources, toxification, and urbanization, has disrupted ecological diversity and caused damage to wildlife.

In nature, there is a balance between the species in a region that creates a healthy ecosystem and any changes in biodiversity can lead to dramatic reduction or extinction of some life forms. The natural ecosystem balance has been affected by climate change in various forms. Temperature increase is affecting the landscape on earth by changes in precipitation, longer summer droughts, glacial melt, reduction in arctic and sea ice, and rising sea levels. These factors directly affect wildlife by change in vegetation, shift in migration paths, reducing the size of some organisms, weakening of their immune system, and increase in population of invasive species and disease vectors. Consequently, any harm to wildlife would affect humans in many ways. For example, wildlife health can be considered one of the key elements to the survival of humans as there are diseases that can be transferred to humans directly, or through domestic animals or vegetation (Ibáñez et al., 2023). The most recent pandemic, believed to have originated from the transfer of disease from wildlife to humans, and its global impact on societies, economies, and politics, demonstrated how humanity responds to ecological disasters.

By admitting the fact that wildlife is crucial to maintain a healthy ecosystem for all species, including humans, in recent decades international organizations have been collaborating with scientists to monitor the effects of climate change on wildlife, and contributing to global plans for wildlife conservation.

Although their biggest concern is how the changes on Earth will affect humans' lives, since humans are part of a larger ecosystem, their activities have potential positive outcomes to help wildlife as well. Over time different available tools such as camera traps, radars, sonar tracers, Global Positioning System (GPS), and satellite imaging have been used to gather vast amounts of data by researchers and various organizations. Mathematical and statistical methods have been used to analyze these data and understand the effect of climate change on the environment, identifying the trend of changes, and predicting the pattern of changes to mitigate, and if possible, reverse these changes.

1.2. Today's Opportunity

Technological advancements in computation and data processing devices in recent years have provided efficiency and accuracy in collecting and analyzing environmental data and biodiversity conditions. These advancements have also introduced new intelligent tools that can be used for complex analysis. Concept of *Artificial Intelligence (AI)* and *Machine Learning (ML)* as we know today can be credited to Allan Turing when in 1950, he asked "*Can Machines Think?*" (Turing, 1950). However, it took decades until the advancements in electronics engineering could provide the required platforms with high computational power to fulfill his idea of a machine that can perform like the human brain. Today, artificial intelligence comprises advanced computational hardware and sophisticated software, which utilizes complex algorithms as its cognitive mechanism.

The current state of technology has made artificial intelligence and machine learning become more available and gain their place in all fields of science. The application of artificial intelligence in environmental studies and wildlife conservation provides the capability of real-time analysis of vast amounts of data to evaluate and predict ecosystems' transformations. Research centers, universities, and other organizations with access to this technology have created *Artificial intelligence-based (AI-based)* tools for all aspects of environmental research, and some have made them available to all scientists. Users can utilize these artificial intelligence-based tools and algorithms for processing their data and in return, this shared technology can access more data than can be obtained by one team with limited resources, especially field data.

1.3. Taking The Opportunity

Although the utilization of artificial intelligence is relatively new to the conservation field, its capabilities make it a suitable tool for the critical subject of climate change and wildlife conservation. This thesis will provide an understanding about how artificial intelligence and machine learning are currently utilized to

mitigate the impacts of climate change on wildlife, what are the limitations and concerns in using such technology, and potential improvements to maximize the utilization of artificial intelligence in this field of science. To this end, the thesis will focus on the following key areas:

- What are the key impacts of climate change on wildlife and their habitats?
- What artificial intelligence technologies are used in wildlife monitoring and data collection?
- What artificial intelligence-based predictive models are used for forecasting climate impacts on wildlife?
- What are the roles of artificial intelligence in habitat restoration and conservation planning?
- What are the challenges and ethical considerations in using artificial intelligence for wildlife conservation?

1.4. Methodology

This thesis applies *Literature Review* to examine a selection of academic papers, case studies, and expert reports related to impacts of climate change on wildlife and application of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation. It explores how shifts in climate have altered the environment on earth, as well as current applications, challenges, and opportunities in artificial intelligence-based solutions used to mitigate these effects on wildlife.

1.5. Coming Next: Structure

Following the introduction, the process of data collection for this research will be outlined. Next, key definitions that are used throughout this research will be introduced. A selection of available literatures will be examined to understand the current stance of the researchers on climate change impacts on wildlife, and how they suggest utilizing artificial intelligence to help wildlife with the effects of climate change. Using these results, important impacts of climate change on wildlife will be categorized and discussed. The current application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in monitoring, data collection, analysis, and prediction of biodiversity changes will be discussed. Furthermore, the limitations, technical and ethical issues that would impact the utilization of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation will be addressed. Next, future research areas will be proposed, and finally, a conclusion will be drawn from the findings, after which recommendations and potential improvements in the effectiveness of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation will be made.

2. Research Methodology

The design and process of search, selection and analysis of the literature used in this thesis are outlined in the current chapter. It outlines the criteria for selection, classification, and analysis of these literatures used as data source for this research.

2.1. Research Design

To achieve the objectives of this thesis, work began with searching for the existing literature in environmental science with a focus on the impacts of climate change on wildlife, conservation methods, computer-based methods, and current applications of artificial intelligence in the field of wildlife conservation and climate change studies.

2.2. Data Collection

2.2.1. Literature Sources

Wildlife conservation science and climate change related publications are commonly published in journals of environmental and biological science. Several digital journals in these fields such as *Conservation Biology* and *Journal of Biogeography* were considered in search for resources for this thesis. In addition to these expert journals, other sources of scholar publications with broader domains including *Google Scholar* and *PubMed* were used to access the publications in the focused areas.

Table 2. List of Search Sources

Type of Source	Name
Scientific Literature Databases	Google Scholar
	PubMed
Environmental and Biological Sciences Journals	Conservation Biology
	Journal of Biogeography
	Nature
	Sustainability
	Wiley Online Library
International Organizations	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)
	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	IUCN Red List of Threatened Species
	United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)
Expert Websites	ESA Climate Change Initiative
	NASA Science - Climate change
	NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies
	WILDLABS
	World Meteorological Organization (WMO)

Source: Author's creation.

Furthermore, the digital reports from Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) were considered as an official global climate change statement. Several official websites such as *International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)* were searched to verify information provided in the literatures, and *WILDLABS* website was examined as it presents a global community of conservation experts and technologies with up-to-date practical data. Table 2 contains a complete list of sources that were used to search for required resources.

2.2.2. Search Criteria

Considering that the application of artificial intelligence has become more available in recent years and the aim for reviewing the current state of this technology in climate change and wildlife studies, search date was set to look for literatures from 2020 onward, except for instances that required accessing influential works prior to that date, such as sixth extinction. Additional filter added to gather results published in English language.

With the objectives of understanding the impacts of climate change on wildlife and how artificial intelligence is utilized to mitigate these impacts, keywords and phrases focusing on these subjects and a combination of them were used that listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Search Keywords and Phrases

Keywords and Phrases	Combinations
climate change	"animal" AND "climate change"
impacts of climate changes on wildlife	"wildlife" AND "climate change"
climate change effects on biodiversity	"wildlife conservation" AND "climate change"
wildlife disease	("wildlife disease" OR "wildlife health") AND "climate change"
human-wildlife conflicts	"human-wildlife conflicts" AND "climate change"
AI in wildlife conservation	"wildlife conservation" AND ("artificial intelligence" OR "machine learning")
AI ethics	("artificial intelligence" OR "machine learning") AND "ethics"
AI ethics in wildlife conservation	"wildlife conservation" AND "AI" AND "ethics"

Source: Author's creation.

2.2.3. Result Selection and Classification

For classification and assessment of the numerous papers resulting from each search, and not being lost or digressed from the main goal of this thesis, a handwritten wall map was created. This map contains important notes related to the objectives of this research and the interconnection between them as guidance for selecting resources. Furthermore, a file with separate tables for the planned categories was created to record important content of papers according to the classification. This author's self-organized preliminary algorithm commenced to unify the selected data for further detailed review (Figure 1). To ensure the quality of resources, it was necessary to select literature from reputable universities and organizations that specialize in wildlife studies, conservation, and artificial intelligence science and technology.

Figure 1. Result Selection

Source: Author's creation.

In the first step of search, approximately 200 papers and reports were retrieved. Next, they were further sorted through reviewing abstracts to ensure the alignment of findings with the requirements of this thesis, which a total of 131 papers were selected for a detailed examination. These publications were labeled in three categories based on the requirements for the objectives of this work. "Climate Change Impacts" focuses on what are the known impacts of climate change on wildlife, "Artificial Intelligence in Conservation" includes the current state of application of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation, and "Issues and Concerns" gathers technical and ethical matters described by selected literatures. This classification helped to organize the information for review and analysis (Figure 2). A more in-depth assessment was conducted on the selected sources to evaluate their significance and contribution to

the objectives of this research. Ultimately, 74 articles were selected for rigorous and comprehensive analysis in this thesis.

Nevertheless, a small number of literatures were found that exclusively concentrated on technical and ethical issues of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation. Most discussions in these subjects were a small section in papers about the application of artificial intelligence in this field.

Figure 2. Result Classification

Source: Author's creation.

2.3. Data Analysis

The systematic review and analysis of acquired resources was conducted in a sequence. Climate change impacts, particularly on wildlife, was the first subject to study as it would provide the foundation for understanding the necessary actions to mitigate or ideally reverse these impacts. Next, the existing artificial intelligence-based solutions that were presented in the selected literatures were examined with the aim of assessing their potential strengths and weaknesses. At the same time, the technical and ethical issues of such solutions that concerned the researchers were reviewed.

Ultimately, these contents were evaluated from the viewpoint of this research to draw conclusion on what is the current state of climate change effects on wildlife and how artificial intelligence can be utilized to assist researchers and conservation organizations to reduce the impact of climate change on wildlife.

3. Theoretical background

This chapter defines key terms used in this thesis, followed by the review of selected literature relevant to the study's subjects.

3.1. Definitions

3.1.1. Climate Change

All forms of life on Earth are fundamentally dependent on the stable climate of their environment. *Climate* is defined by a long-term pattern of weather conditions at a particular geographical location, and this pattern can extend from months to millions of years (Climate Change - NASA Science, n.d.; European Space Agency, n.d.). In contrast, *Weather* refers to the local state of atmosphere at a specific or short periods of time (from minutes to days), and characterized by temperature, precipitation, wind, and such atmospheric variables (Climate Change - NASA Science, n.d.; European Space Agency, n.d.).

Figure 3. Weather vs Climate

Source: European Space Agency – ESA

Accordingly, *Climate Change* is described as a change in the climate pattern over an extended period, typically spanning a decade or longer (World Meteorological Organization, n.d.). Although this term is often used interchangeably with *Global Warming*, the latter specifically refers to the long-term increase in global surface temperature, compared to the baseline of 1850-1900, due to human activities (Climate Change - NASA Science, n.d.). The *Greenhouse Effect* maintains a stable climate on Earth by absorbing

and emitting part of solar radiation to Earth's surface to keep the temperature stable. There are atmospheric particles in the form of gas that contribute to this effect, known as *Greenhouse Gases*, including carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), ozone (O₃), and water vapor (H₂O) (British Geological Survey, 2024). The primary source of current *Anthropogenic* (human-caused) climate change is the increasing amount of carbon dioxide released from burning fossil fuels since the 18th century (Climate Change - NASA Science, n.d.). The amount of greenhouse gases emitted from activities or devices, which measured by its equivalent of carbon dioxide, indicates the *Carbon Footprint* of the activity or device (Cowls et al., 2021).

Figure 4. The Greenhouse Effect

Source: British Geological Survey (2023)

3.1.2. Wildlife

Wildlife refers to species of organisms, including plants, animals, and microbes that live wild in a natural environment. More scientific description requires the organism to be non-domesticated and native to their living environment by humans (Usher, 1986). Accordingly, *Wildlife Conservation* refers to the protection of wild species and their habitats (Encyclopedia Britannica, n.d.). A key aspect of a species' life is *Phenology*, the timing of annual recurring life events, such as breeding, hibernation, migration, or pollination. Any alteration in this timing significantly impacts ecosystems and the species within them (Inouye, 2022; Encyclopedia Britannica, n.d.). *Ecosystem* refers to a community of living organisms, referred to as *biotic members*, and their non-living environment known as *abiotic elements* (IPCC, 2023; Encyclopedia Britannica, n.d.). Furthermore, all varieties of life on earth, from genes to species, and ecosystems are referred to as *Biodiversity* (Silvestro et al., 2022; IPCC, 2023). An important method to understand changes in wildlife is *Species Distribution Modeling*, a model of prediction in conservation which can plot the habitat of species and predict their future distribution based on environmental data

(Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020). Knowledge of ecosystems, their native biodiversity, and distribution of species is a key to identifying *Invasive Alien Species (AIS)*, the nonnative organisms that are introduced by humans or as a result of climate change (Encyclopedia Britannica, n.d.; IUCN, n.d.).

3.1.3. Artificial Intelligence

The idea of a machine that can think, learn, and perform like an intelligent being (Turing, 1950) introduced the fundamental concepts for *Artificial Intelligence (AI)*, the intelligent agent that can make rational decisions to take the best possible actions to solve a problem (Russell & Norvig, 2021, p. 22). Such an intelligent agent is a machine (computer) that uses algorithms to learn from existing data to make predictions and decisions. *Machine Learning (ML)* is an algorithmic method used by computers to build models from available data, enabling autonomous learning (Russell & Norvig, 2021, p. 669; Encyclopedia Britannica, n.d.). These methods can be categorized under three major approaches, *Supervised Learning*, *Unsupervised Learning*, and *Reinforced Learning*.

In supervised learning, the agent is provided by labeled input data and the correspondent output to build the model's algorithm. Later, the agent utilizes this model to process environmental data and make the correct decision (Russell & Norvig, 2021, p. 671).

Figure 5. Supervised Learning

This figure depicts supervised learning stages: A) Model Training, B) Identifying New Data from the Environment, C) Anomaly Detection. Source: Author's creation, based on the concept of Supervised Learning.

Supervised learning methods are particularly useful for data classification, image recognition, anomaly detection, and prediction.

Unsupervised learning allows the agent to identify the patterns in the unlabeled input data (Russell & Norvig, 2021, p. 671). This method is commonly used to detect patterns in large datasets, with the purpose of dimensionality reduction or data clustering (Pichler & Hartig, 2023). Therefore, it can identify anomalous data points that do not fit in the detected pattern.

Figure 6. Unsupervised Learning

Data clustering by unsupervised learning. Source: Author's creation, based on the concept of Unsupervised Learning.

Reinforcement learning utilizes a reward and punishment system to train an agent, a model initially suggested by Turing in 1950, similar to teaching a human child (Turing, 1950).

Figure 7. Reinforcement Learning

Source: Author's creation, based on the concept of Reinforcement Learning.

The agent takes action to move from the current state to the next, exploring the environment (e.g., a scenario, problem, or prediction). It receives feedback in the form of a reward or punishment. These actions continue in sequences until the goal is achieved while maximizing the reward (Russell & Norvig, 2021, p. 671, 840).

To improve the learning performance, a combination of different machine learning models can be used as *Ensemble Learning* or *Ensemble Method* (Pichler & Hartig, 2023). Nevertheless, training a machine learning model for a specific task requires large datasets and computational power, which is costly and time consuming. *Transfer Learning* is a method that uses a machine learning algorithm that was trained for a task, to solve another related task (Wang & Chen, 2023, p. 5).

The logical mapping of neural activities of brain by McCulloch and Pitts (1943) laid the foundation for the architecture of *Neural Network (NN)*, machine learning algorithms that mimic the human brain by using mathematical models as neurons, to achieve a higher level of accuracy in complex decision-making tasks (Russell & Norvig, 2021, p. 801; Borowiec et al., 2022).

Figure 8. Overview of a Neural Network

Source: Author's creation, based on the concept of Neural Networks.

Deep Learning (DL) is a subset of machine learning that uses multiple layers (deep layers) of neural networks to enhance machine learning solutions (Russell & Norvig, 2021, p. 801).

Figure 9. Interrelations of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Deep Learning

Source: Author's creation.

Various architectures of neural networks are used in machine learning solutions, with *Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)* being the most common architecture for computer vision, image processing, voice recognition, and medical imaging. In this architecture, images pass through multiple layers, with each layer detecting and extracting specific elements of images until they are fully recognized (Russell & Norvig, 2021, p. 811; Borowiec et al., 2022). In the absence of large training datasets, convolutional neural networks can be trained on synthetic data, to improve the accuracy of recognizing specific objects (De Wilde et al., 2024).

Figure 10. Overview of a Convolutional Neural Network

Source: Author's creation, based on the concept of Convolutional Neural Networks. Image: Microsoft Office 365.

Convolutional neural network models used for image classification require large datasets of images for training. When such a large amount of data is not available, additional variations of images can be produced with *Data Augmentation*, which involves manipulation of images by resizing, flipping, distorting, or changing color palette. (Hua et al., 2022; Brito et al., 2024; Delplanque et al., 2024).

3.2. Literature Review

This literature review aimed to provide an overview of existing research areas on climate change, its impacts on wildlife, and applied artificial intelligence solutions assisting to study and reduce these impacts. Research topics are categorized based on major subjects that are widely studied.

3.2.1. Impacts of Climate Change on Wildlife

Research evidence shows the anthropogenic climate change has caused higher global temperatures. NASA report shows that 2023 has been the warmest year on record since 1880. Earth was overall 1.36 degrees Celsius warmer than early 1900s (Climate Change - NASA Science, n.d.). Global warming is proven through the unusual heatwaves, droughts, abnormal precipitation, rise of sea level, and decline of Arctic ice. These events have had extreme impacts on all ecosystems that pushed some of them to

an irreversible level, with several species already becoming extinct (IPCC, 2023). With the extensive diversity of ecosystems on Earth, scientists and experts have published a considerable number of research papers and data about these disruptions that are affecting various aspects of wildlife. A selection of these literatures concerning such impacts on different ecosystems and species is reviewed in this section.

- **Geographical Shift and Habitat Loss**

Species live in a certain geographical range with specific environment and when the ecological conditions change, they shift their habitat towards an area that provides proper conditions (Pecl et al., 2023). Consequently, increased temperature has been pushing many species towards colder areas with higher altitudes or latitudes (IPCC, 2023). A study on shorebirds in Arctic Canada shows that because this area has become warmer, bird species that regularly breed in that area have shifted their breeding habitat towards north (Anderson et al., 2023). Remarkably, this migration trend towards higher latitudes was observed in temperate tree species in Canada. This habitat extension is the result of rising temperature and creating favorable environment for the seeds of these trees to grow in higher latitudes (Boisvert-Marsh & De Blois, 2021). In the Central European and Alps mountains these shifts required species of bird to move to higher altitudes in search of viable conditions (Fumy & Fartmann, 2021). While studies show the same movement in tropical mountain forests, in many cases it is not sustainable due to limitation of physical space (Mata-Guel et al., 2023). Rising temperatures have similarly affected the marine ecosystem. A global analysis by Hastings et al. (2020) on the abundance of various marine species such as phytoplankton, fish, mammals, and seabirds concluded that they have been moving polewards as a result of warming oceans.

Climate change has altered seasonal events, specifically in the Arctic, resulting in warmer summers, decline in land and sea ice, and shorter sea ice duration (Perovich et al., 2020). These disruptions have severely impacted Arctic species' habitats. The effect of such changes was studied in Southeast Greenland by Heide-Jørgensen et al. (2022). Their study shows that the elevated temperature has caused a reduction in sea ice in the summer, which impacted the ecosystem and altered the marine biodiversity of this area. The research on Arctic fox in Hudson Bay, Canada by Verstege et al. (2023) suggests that these changes in Arctic climate have impacted their habitat and consequently the food sources, causing a decrease in their population. Conversely, these changes have not influenced the life of the red fox to the same degree, as it adapts well to warmer weather and has a broader diet.

Additionally, climate change's contribution to land degradation is reported by IPCC (2023). This report is confident that in the last 100 years, nearly 50% of coastal wetlands have been lost due to climate

change. This alteration in habitat and the poleward shift have been observed in all ecosystems in various forms, which requires constant monitoring from environmental science experts.

- **Altered Migration Patterns**

Scientists in the field of phenology have observed changes in migration behavior of species with periodical migration in the form of altered migration cycles and paths. Animals and plants have been using the transformation pattern of environmental temperature, and the timing and levels of precipitation to determine life events such as hibernation, reproduction, and migration (Vitasse et al., 2021; Inouye, 2022). Global climate anomalies, such as elevated temperatures in typically cold seasons, impacted the phenological life events of species, including migration time, by changing the patterns of these events (Inouye, 2022).

Whitin migratory species, several species of birds are known for their migration between breeding locations and wintering areas. In the study on a few species of birds that passing through Mai Po Nature Reserve in Hong Kong, Allcock et al. (2022) discovered later arrival date in their migration. They suggested that the impact of climate change on seasonal temperature has shifted their migration time over an 11-year study period. In a study on a group of GPS-tracked swans, Linssen et al. (2023) concluded that swans fly longer distances on autumn days with lower temperatures, to reach their wintering grounds. However, since climate change has decreased the number of cooler days in autumn, now they can only travel a short distance from their breeding areas.

The change in migration pattern has also been observed in marine species by researchers. Crear et al. (2022) that studied migratory fish species such as tuna, have observed shift in their migration data. Their findings indicate that water temperature influenced the timing of fish arrival and departure from spawn area, which results in longer stay. Similarly, Kanamori et al. (2023) analysis of five decades of data indicates that migration season for the Pacific spiny dogfish in the Sea of Japan (East Sea) has become a month earlier after year 2000. They suggested that the increase in sea surface temperature is a cause of this phenological change.

- **Reproduction Abnormality**

The reproductive process in wildlife is the critical factor in preventing the extinction of species. Studies on global warming indicate negative effects on the reproduction of many species. As explained in the previous section, reproduction is a phenological event that is believed to be altered by climate change (Vitasse et al., 2021; Inouye, 2022). A study on arctic ground squirrels by Chmura et al. (2023) suggests the shift in freezing time has altered the hibernation period, therefore female animals starting their active season earlier than male. They argue that this mismatch in activation time affects their breeding period.

Further impact of rising temperature has been studied on sea turtles in multiple conservation areas (Lockley & Eizaguirre, 2021). Results indicate the change in the climate increased the hatching of sea female turtles. This imbalance in genders can lead to the extinction of this animal. Lockley and Eizaguirre (2021) believe that warming climate can affect over 400 species that gender of their offsprings depends on the temperature of their nest and environment (*Temperature-dependent Sex Determination*).

The alteration in reproduction has not only been observed in animals. Inouye (2022) suggested that the phenology of Rocky Mountain flowers has been impacted by warmer climate. The study's data indicates earlier flowering dates and extended flowering season due to earlier snow melting season. Therefore, these early flowers can be affected by the last spring frost in June. Consequently, the population of a type of butterfly that depends on the nectar of these flowers will decline due to decrease in their food source.

- **Rate of Disease Transmission**

Researchers have been investigating the increase of wildlife diseases along with the rise in global temperature, for potential connection between these phenomena. However, the number of available literatures focusing on such correlation is limited in contrary to similar research on human diseases (Van De Vuurst & Escobar, 2023). Nevertheless, there is consensus regarding the indirect impact of climate change on increasing wildlife diseases, which is attributed to geographical, and habitat shift of species that carry them to new areas (Pilfold et al., 2021; Pecl et al., 2023). In their research on terrestrial and freshwater species, Cohen et al. (2020) concluded that temperature abnormalities can increase the risk of diseases. They further stated that climate change may increase this risk in species that live in cooler climate conditions (cold-adapted) since their immune systems are thermosensitive.

A similar correlation was studied by Sanderson and Alexander (2020) on marine mammals' infectious disease. Their data analysis indicates sea surface temperature anomalies can weaken the immune system of these mammals. A study on polar bear antibodies by Pilfold et al. (2021) suggested climate change is linked to an increase in the infection rates of specific pathogens in polar bears. Their analysis of data collected between 1986 and 2017 in Hudson Bay, Canada, indicated a positive correlation between the infection rate of certain pathogens and climate factors such as warmer winters, hotter summers, abnormal precipitation, and an increased number of ice-free days. However, these studies emphasize the need for more research on this correlation between climate change and wildlife diseases.

- **Human and Wildlife Conflicts**

Climatic changes have disrupted ecosystems and wildlife habitats. Droughts have impacted terrestrial ecosystems with vegetation loss and resource scarcity, which forced wildlife to migrate in search of food

sources. Abrahms (2021) explained that these geographical shifts in some regions have led wildlife to human-dominated areas, creating shared landscapes and resulting in human-wildlife conflicts. Several cases of humans harmed by wildlife have been reported and studied in different regions.

Newsom et al. (2023) conducted a scientific analysis of several reports on human-wildlife encounters from 44 countries, including terrestrial and aquatic species. They concluded that the impacts of climate change on ecosystems resulting in environmental disruptions have influenced these conflicts. This analysis indicated that warmer winters, reduced Arctic ice, droughts, and other extreme weather events, which cause food scarce and habitat shifts, are factors that increase these conflicts. Similarly, Shiweda et al. (2023) concluded that droughts resulting from warming climate in Namibia have shifted the habitat of elephants closer to commercial farms, increasing human-elephant conflicts.

Human-wildlife conflicts are reported in all regions where the impacts of climate change have shifted wildlife habitats (Brackowski et al., 2023; Guarnieri et al., 2024). The marine system has been similarly affected by rising sea temperature (Abrahms, 2021). In the West Coast of the United States, the rising sea temperature has altered the ecosystem and food source for whales. This shift has caused whales to move further north and closer to the shore for new food sources, resulting in their entanglement in fishing equipment (Santora et al., 2020).

3.2.2. Application of Artificial Intelligence in Wildlife Conservation

In response to the impacts of global warming, various international and intergovernmental organizations have been working on plans and policies to mitigate these effects or adapt to the new states where possible. Although there are difficulties in the implementation of these strategies, technological innovations can provide speed, precision, and efficiency in executing such solutions. As described in the IPCC report (2023), digital technologies including artificial intelligence can be used in many ways to improve the efficient and sustainable use of resources, as well as reducing greenhouse gases as the main cause of anthropogenic climate change. Researchers have been utilizing technological solutions in environmental studies and wildlife conservation as they became available. The recent advancements in artificial intelligence created opportunities for experts in this field to benefit from artificial intelligence-based solutions. This section examines the commonly applied methods.

- **Biodiversity Monitoring**

Monitoring and tracking species have been used in ecosystem studies and conservation, and with the current climate crisis, real-time awareness of ecosystem changes is crucial to understanding the effects of habitat changes and how species react and adapt to these changes. Lahoz-Monfort and Magrath

(2021) provided a comprehensive overview of technological devices that are used to gather data in the forms of images, voices, temperature, or seismic records. This substantial amount of data is required to be processed to detect and distinguish natural changes and irregularities, which is challenging (Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021). Artificial intelligence provides the solution for processing high volumes of data using machine learning methods such as deep learning algorithms. Its advantage of real-time data processing to detect and track species presents the opportunity to accurately observe their migration pattern, habitat, food sources, and their response to environmental changes (Liu et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022; Rubbens et al., 2023).

An interesting study on elephant monitoring in Africa by Brickson et al. (2023) suggested a combination of data collecting methods could be used in wildlife monitoring. In their proposed solution, images gathered by *Unmanned Aerial Vehicles* (UAVs), camera traps, and satellites will be processed by deep learning methods to detect elephants and their movements. Remote sensing combined with machine learning algorithms, as described in several literatures, is a common artificial intelligence-based monitoring method in wildlife conservation (Tuia et al., 2022; Rubbens et al., 2023). These machine learning solutions utilize deep learning algorithms, such as convolutional neural networks, which are trained on datasets consisting of species images for object identification and classification (Buchelt et al., 2024).

According to Brickson et al. (2023), captured videos can be further processed by machine learning-based (ML-based) behavioral analysis models, to interpret animals' visual communications. Furthermore, the same study describes how seismic and even olfactory monitoring data can be analyzed through machine learning methods for wildlife conservation. Similarly, machine learning can help to analyze recorded voices to recognize specific species and their communications (Tuia et al., 2022; Román Ruiz et al., 2023; Batist et al., 2024).

A cost-effective solution that used machine learning to process images taken by drones, was implemented and tested by Hua et al. (2022) in Namibia. They used a convolutional neural network installed on a lightweight computer with data storage (edge computer) designed to mount on autonomous machines. Due to the limited data availability, they utilized image augmentation techniques to increase the data required for successful model training. Their solution was designed to detect endangered megafauna and send a notification along with the geolocation of the animal. They concluded that their solution is suitable for areas with limited technological and communication resources, by achieving accuracy in detection and minimum usage of communication bandwidth. However, they expressed their concern about accessing such solutions by poachers and hunters, as hardware technology and open-source software are available to the public.

Delplanque et al. (2024) examined a machine learning-based model to introduce a semi-automated solution for oblique-camera-count (OCC). The current method consists of using digital cameras on both sides of an airplane to take pictures of groups of animals in a region and later those pictures would be manually reviewed to count animals in that area. They used a pre-trained model and fine-tuned it for their task (transfer learning) by two steps of manual classification. Results of this model suggested more accuracy compared to the manual count, especially for certain groups of animals. The team concluded that, even though their model requires refining, this method can replace the manual counting and also, images can be taken by unmanned aerial vehicles instead of airplanes.

A case of using machine learning models for classification was experimented by Blair et al. (2023). They compared convolutional neural network models with *Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM)* and *Random Forest (RF)* algorithms to classify species of ground beetles. The results of comparison of those models with the same image datasets concluded that convolutional neural networks were high-speed models with good overall performance for their case.

Patton et al. (2023) introduced a convolutional neural network-based model with the ability to automatically identify multiple marine mammal species. They trained their model with images of dorsal fins from 24 distinct species. Their evaluation of a large test dataset accomplished an overall 86.9% mean average precision, which they considered it a high predictive performance. This team concluded that the angle and quality of images would affect the prediction, as well as pigmented species or individuals with unusual marks on their fins.

Monitoring rare species through machine learning is more difficult due to limited visual data. Brito et al. (2024) conducted research to utilize machine learning for detecting several endangered species threatened by mining industry in Chile. Since these species are rare and the number of their images was limited, they utilized data augmentation to increase the dataset. Next, they used transfer learning and tuned a pretrained convolutional neural network model for image classification. Based on the accuracy of the results, they suggest that the combination of data augmentation and transfer learning can be effective on small image datasets, when the machine learning model is pretrained with images of animals similar to the subjects of classification.

Acoustic data analysis is a method that is used in species detection for wildlife monitoring. Román Ruiz et al. (2023) examined a method based on convolutional neural network to detect presence of fin whales by identifying their voice pulses (calls). They used software with Fourier transform method to convert audio files to images for training and evaluating the model. Next, they examined the model with 3 months of recording and stated that the detection results were satisfactory. In their experiment they also compared the convolutional neural network with two other machine learning models and concluded that

convolutional neural networks are effective models for such classification as their performance can improve with more datasets being available.

Another study that used acoustic data was conducted on detecting an endangered species of Lemures (black-and-white ruffed lemur) in Madagascar. Batist et al. (2024) experimented with the application of convolutional neural network to analyze the recorded voices of the animal for detecting their presence in a specific area (passive acoustic monitoring or PAM). They used software to visualize and manually annotate the animal's voice to prepare image files. A number of these files were then used to retrain and fine-tune an already trained model (transfer learning), and another part of data to evaluate the performance of the model. They stated that their model showed high accuracy on two datasets with less surrounding noise. Furthermore, they concluded that voices recorded by a set of identical and reliable devices could improve their model.

Similar to animal surveillance, artificial intelligence-based image processing is an important technique in monitoring the ecosystem of forests. As explained by Buchelt et al. (2024), analyzing the images captured by drones provides an opportunity to detect illnesses in trees and take preventive actions to avoid impacting a widespread infection. Since with extended drought periods and higher temperatures, wildfires have been occurring more often, they concluded that accurate data processing using machine learning helps to detect wildfires quickly and prevent them from spreading. Furthermore, they suggested that machine learning models can add autonomy to drone flights to minimize human interaction in forest monitoring.

The purpose of wildlife monitoring is not only to track the species, but it also helps to detect unusual material in their ecosystems. Wolf et al. (2020) provided a convolutional neural network algorithm that detects floating plastic litter in aerial images taken from shores. This solution provides a precise location that requires cleaning, to prevent harm to aquatic species.

- **Predictive Models of Changes**

The alarming rate of biodiversity loss demands effective data-driven strategies for wildlife conservation. Biodiversity monitoring methods provide a wide range of data from various aspects of wildlife (Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021). Analyzing this data using machine learning algorithms can help scientists to create models of ecosystems to simulate and predict the potential changes in them (Chen et al., 2023). A simple, but crucial case is weather forecasting that machine learning models can increase the accuracy in prediction of severe climatic events such as droughts (Cowl et al., 2021; Leal Filho et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2023).

Species distribution modeling, an important model of prediction in conservation, benefits from the machine learning algorithms as Mosebo Fernandes et al. (2020) experimented in their research on

habitat prediction for Sage-grouse in Utah, United States. They used four machine learning algorithms to train the data collected by volunteers for *Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)*. The trained models assessed different future climate scenarios, and the results indicated this bird will lose 60% of its habitat in the next 30-40 years, if global warming increases 3 degrees Celsius. It also highlighted that the lack of current data for variables can reduce the accuracy of some artificial intelligence-based solutions. Furthermore, they confirmed that the accuracy level of datasets can influence the results, introducing potential bias and errors. Nevertheless, this experiment suggested that machine learning models increase the speed and accuracy of species distribution modeling to assess various scenarios.

Evaluating the extinction threat for species is a sensitive and crucial step in biodiversity assessment and conservation planning. The International Union for Conservation of Nature has been collecting data of various species and created the *Red List of Threatened Species (IUCN Red List)* based on extinction threat for endangered species. However, this organization has evaluated the extinction risk for only 8% of all species that their data is available (IUCN, 2024; Silva et al., 2022). Therefore, the application of artificial intelligence models in this time-sensitive case can expedite the evaluation process. A study was conducted by Silva et al. (2022) to automatically assess the extinction risk for species of trees, based on certain variables including climate and presence of humans in their habitat. They trained two neural network models, a classifier and a regression model, using globally available data and the criteria of the Red List categories for classification. The trained models were used to predict the risk for a set of unlabeled data, where the classifier showed a higher accuracy. Their model showed that a large number of trees are at risk of extinction in Brazil and Madagascar, with extinction has already been occurring. They concluded their model and similar risk assessment solutions can help to make efficient conservation decisions before the loss of biodiversity.

With the increase in online platforms for volunteers and amateur nature enthusiasts to upload their observation data, Capinha et al. (2024) introduced a framework for using *citizen science* data to predict phenological events for adult stage of Japanese beetles and Winter Chanterelle mushrooms fruiting. They collected data from various citizen science platforms that have potential for biased or incomplete data, thus their model included a method to minimize the bias in the acquired data. Although they acknowledged that their approach has limitations with the missing data points, they concluded that their predictions were close to observed patterns of both phenological events, with better performance from Japanese beetles' adult stage prediction model.

- **Artificial intelligence-based Mitigation Solutions**

Environmental scientists have been analyzing climate and ecosystems data to develop solutions that align with existing policies and conservation strategies. As artificial intelligence-based tools become

more accessible, they can now recommend the most effective conservation strategies to policymakers and decision-makers (Scoville et al., 2021). Silvestro et al. (2022) developed an artificial intelligence-based framework that simulates biodiversity evolution over time in response to climate change and human disruptions, based on a user-defined conservation target. They stated that this algorithm can help to design conservation policies and evaluate their long-term and short-term effects by simulating these effects. They conducted several simulation experiments and concluded that their approach can potentially be a useful method for policymakers to plan localized policy objectives and optimize them before applying to the environment.

A more practical mitigation solution proposed by Castro et al. (2024) for forest restoration. Their proposed method is to employ machine learning models to guide drones for precision sowing. In this approach, small ecologically suitable planting sites (microsites) were chosen for capturing high resolution aerial images to show the acceptable conditions for planting. These images were manually annotated and labeled by experts to train a convolutional neural network model. The trained model can identify planting sites from images sent by drones and guide them to plant seeds in those sites. They concluded that such a solution could increase the planting precision, especially in hard-to-reach areas, while reducing the waste of seeds and cost of operation.

Nevertheless, artificial intelligence models can help with understanding climate change as a broad issue, which would suggest effective solutions to reduce its impact on environment and consequently wildlife (Cowls et al., 2021). Although it is late to reverse certain climate change disruptions, artificial intelligence models can suggest solutions to reduce energy consumption and carbon emission, natural resource management, and reduce the environmental impacts of human activities (Chen et al., 2023).

- **Poaching and Trafficking Detection**

Wildlife monitoring includes the protection of wildlife, particularly endangered species. Accelerated human intrusion detection to alarm rangers is a mechanism that can be empowered by machine learning-based methods from aerial images (Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021; Nandutu et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022).

A preventive solution was proposed and evaluated by de Knegt et al. (2021) that uses machine learning algorithms to detect poachers' intrusion, by observing the change to the movements of a group of sentinel animals in African savanna. They collected GPS and tri-axial accelerometer sensor data from four species in a protected area when humans approached them on foot and on motorized vehicles. With 86.1% accuracy, their model demonstrated that the characteristics and direction of animal movements in response to human intrusions can be used to identify poachers' intrusions while it is happening. For timely detection and locating poachers, this method requires a real-time data

transmission network to collect and transfer data to a data warehouse for processing in the shortest amount of time. However, this could make the application of such a system in a large area challenging and costly.

The solution proposed by Hua et al. (2022), which was previously explained in “Biodiversity Monitoring” in this subsection, is likely to be a low-cost and feasible solution, as it could operate with limited communication bandwidth. As they demonstrated, their lightweight machine learning model on the drone-mounted edge computer can rapidly process live images. They further indicated that their model could notify the anti-poaching patrols or conservation teams by sending images and geolocation in real-time when detecting poachers’ intrusions.

Along with other businesses, wildlife traffickers have employed online services for their activities. Although these trades are mostly done in physical markets (wet markets), traffickers are using social media and other online platforms to advertise and trade (Cardoso et al., 2023; Kulkarni & Di Minin, 2023). In a study, Cardoso et al. (2023) experimented with a machine learning method to detect trading of wildlife on the internet, with focus on species of Pangolin as a test case. This study utilized publicly available deep learning models for image classification and detection of pangolin or its parts. They used online image sources to collect the training dataset, labeled and classified them to train the models. Their study reported that the model used for their case could identify over 90% of the animal’s trades. Furthermore, this study advised that data collection must be expanded to more online platforms, to reduce the lack of access to real trading platforms to obtain images.

Similarly, Kulkarni and Di Minin (2023) utilized a convolutional neural network model to detect wild mammals’ images posted online for trading. Their model was trained with images obtained from a platform that is known for posting images of mammals for sale. They concluded that the model performed with high precision to detect animals in captivity in online images. This study similarly stated that the limited training data from trading platforms influenced the accuracy of the trained model. Both latter studies concluded that these machine learning models can be employed by law enforcement to automatically identify wildlife trades on web platforms.

- **Technical and Ethical Challenges**

Although artificial intelligence has been shown as a powerful technology to improve research and development of climate change and wildlife conservation solutions, it raises a critical ethical concern: potential bias in data or algorithms (Galaz et al., 2021). Accuracy of training data is essential to achieve a reliable machine learning model, therefore high-quality and unbiased data is crucial to this achievement (Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020; Scoville et al., 2021; Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022). In addition to the expert data-collection methods, citizen science platforms have been used for crowdsourcing

environmental data (Palmer et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022). This data is collected by volunteers and community members, increasing the potential for noise and bias, especially due to data quality (Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020; Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022). Since data is collected by various methods, transforming and combining different datasets can lead to noise (Branco et al., 2023). Furthermore, machine learning models that are trained with noisy or biased data can take them as their decision-making parameters, introducing model bias to the solution. (Cowls et al., 2021; Nandutu et al., 2021; Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022; Tuia et al., 2022).

Another issue arises from publicly accessible data. Such data is associated with a considerable risk of exposing geographical location of protected species. Sharing such data with wrong users (e.g., poachers or traffickers) puts the security of species, conservation areas, and staff at risk. (Nandutu et al., 2021; Palmer et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022). Moreover, as indicated by Scoville et al. (2021), with the increase in the number of private companies that provide and control artificial intelligence solutions, there is more potential to influence data and furthermore, decision-making for wildlife conservation.

Cowls et al. (2021) and Tuia et al. (2022) pointed to computation cost of training artificial intelligence models as a challenge for utilizing them in climate change study. Machine learning models require high computational power, which increases with complexity of models and volume of data grow. They further suggested that, besides the financial cost of hardware and computing time, the carbon emissions resulting from producing the computers, shipping, and the energy they use to process data and train the models, should be considered in environmental projects.

4. Research Results and Discussion

The findings of this study are further analyzed in this chapter. It explores the impacts of climate change on wildlife and how artificial intelligence has been employed to study and mitigate some of these impacts.

4.1. Climate Change

Research shows our planet has experienced several climate periods over millions of years that formed various forms of life during each period. While the past climate eras were only influenced by natural elements, the current changes in the climate have additional cause: human activities. Normal climate on Earth is maintained by greenhouse effect, which is created by carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide, ozone, and water vapor in atmosphere. Since the industrial revolution in the 1700s, humans have heavily relied on fossil fuels that contribute to extra emissions of greenhouse gases to the atmosphere. These additional greenhouse gases are equal to their natural change in the past 800,000 years (IPCC, 2023) that caused the anthropogenic climate change.

Figure 11. Earth's Surface Temperature Increase

Source: Author's creation. Data source: NASA's Goddard Institute for Space Studies. Image: Microsoft Office 365.

Scientific evidence of rapid climate change is undeniable. Global rise in surface temperature of Earth has been recorded by various organizations (Figure 11), showing 2023 was 1.36 degrees Celsius warmer than end of 19th century (IPCC, 2023; Climate Change - NASA Science, n.d.).

Figure 12. Oceans Heat Content Change Since 1992

The zettajoule is equal to one sextillion (10^{21}) joules, the unit of heat energy. Source: Author's creation. Data source: NASA ECCO. Image: Microsoft Office 365.

Data shows the temperature rise has also increased the ocean heat content in recent decades (Figure 12). Warming lands and oceans have caused the ice sheets to melt, particularly in the Arctic, resulting in reducing the amount of ice on Earth (Figure 13). Glaciers are shrinking or disappearing, and mountain snow is melting faster, reducing the seasonal snow cover and thus freshwater sources. Melting sea ice is increasing sea levels, potentially resulting in loss of coastal wetlands (Heide-Jørgensen et al., 2022; Perovich et al., 2020; IPCC, 2023; Climate Change - NASA Science, n.d.). Changes in the climate have also increased extreme climate events such as extended droughts, extreme heat waves, increase in wildfires, and irregular precipitation patterns (IPCC, 2023; Climate Change - NASA Science, n.d.). While the reports indicate that certain damage caused by climate change is irreversible, global organizations and governments have been trying to set policies and strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate

change and slow the pace of global temperature increase. However, the majority of the mitigation efforts are human-centric, and some solutions have negative impacts on wildlife.

Figure 13. Average Sea Ice Area in Northern and Southern Hemisphere, 1978-2023

Source: Author's creation. Data source: National Snow and Ice Data Center (Fetterer et al., 2017). Image: Microsoft Office 365.

4.2. Impacts on Wildlife

The altered climate patterns have impacted Earth's ecosystems, directly or through a chain of events, and altered their biodiversity. The impacts of climate change on wildlife can be categorized as geographical shift and habitat loss, change in rate of disease transmission, reproduction abnormality, altered migration patterns, and human-wildlife conflicts.

Plant species provide habitat and food for many other biotic members of ecosystems. Increase in the temperature, extreme heat, and extended droughts reduced the vegetation on land, caused extinction of some plant species and are threatening the existence of many others. Consequently, other species

that depend on these plants had to move to areas with available vegetation to survive. Although some organisms have been attempting to adapt to the change of vegetation, most of the species have been gradually migrating polewards to areas with favorable temperatures (IPCC, 2023; Pecl et al., 2023). Astonishingly, certain species of plants in the northern hemisphere have been expanding towards higher latitudes, as temperatures rise created a favorable habitat for their growth. Additionally, some of the species that depend on these plants may change their geographical location with them. However, geographical shifts are not always sustainable, particularly in mountain ecosystems, as the extent to which organisms can relocate is limited (Boisvert-Marsh & De Blois, 2021; Fumy & Fartmann, 2021; Vitasse et al., 2021; Mata-Guel et al., 2023). Similar problems with habitat loss have been observed in marine ecosystems. Increase in ocean heat content has altered the habitat and life of ocean flora and fauna. Organisms have been attempting to adapt to the changes, but they have reached their limits and are gradually moving towards cooler areas (Hastings et al., 2020; IPCC, 2023).

Figure 14. Glacier and Ice Cap Loss in Northwest Greenland

Images taken 49 years apart showing the decline in glaciers and ice caps in northeast Greenland: A) September 2nd, 1973, B) August 20th, 2022. Source: NASA Earth Observatory, images by Joshua Stevens.

Climate change impacts on the Arctic region have been more severe and caused a decrease in the snow layer, ice sheets, surface ice and sea ice, the habitats for Arctic fauna (Figure 14). Warmer and longer summers along with shorter winters, have delayed and shortened the freeze-up period, impacting the breeding time and food availability for these species. Furthermore, warmer weather has transformed the ecosystem of the region by drawing new species seeking a suitable environment from lower latitudes due to the same reason. Certain regions are home to Arctic and warmer-weather animals in different seasons, but climate change has caused an imbalance between the abundance of these groups of wildlife. This is the direct result of decline in the surface ice that naturally provides a favorable environment for seasonal migratory birds, mammals, and marine species for breeding and hunting (Heide-Jørgensen et al., 2022; Verstege et al., 2023).

With habitat loss and geographical shifts of species, biodiversity of departure and destination areas are altered, creating an environment for invasive alien species that can disrupt the balance of ecosystem, and lead to the extinction of local species. Parasites and pathogens show an increase in their activities as a result of temperature anomalies and geographical shift of species. Warmer environments create an ideal habitat for such microorganisms, particularly when their hosts have a weak immune system. Furthermore, global warming and disruption of habitat weaken the immune system of species, which makes them more vulnerable to infectious disease. This impact is more severe in cold-adapted species as they are facing warmer winters and other climate anomalies (Cohen et al., 2020; Sanderson & Alexander, 2020; Pilfold et al., 2021; Pecl et al., 2023).

Natural phenological events occur based on seasonal changes. Organisms rely on weather elements and environmental changes as a calendar for their life events. Migration, hibernation, and breeding seasons are determined by changes in temperature, humidity, and precipitation. Climate change has disrupted the natural timing of these elements, altering the sequence of life events. Hibernator animals follow the temperature changes as an indicator for change in season (Vitasse et al., 2021; Inouye, 2022). Shorter, warmer winters and delay in land freeze date, have altered their hibernation period, leading to difficulties in finding food, weakening their body, and irregular breeding patterns. Similarly, pollination of plant species is impacted by shift in seasons and weather elements. Early growth and flowering, followed by spring freeze can affect plants, resulting in a decrease in available food for pollinators, and decline in plant populations (Vitasse et al., 2021; Inouye, 2022; Chmura et al., 2023). Additionally, over 400 species of animals with temperature-dependent sex determination (TSD) are directly affected by global warming. Warmer hatching season is increasing the number of one gender, and this disparity between the number of males and females is endangering this group of animals and can drive them to extinction (Lockley & Eizaguirre, 2021).

The survival of many terrestrial and aquatic animals depends on the seasonal migration between breeding and winter areas. The change in climate has disrupted the travel time, distance, and geographical direction for these species. Temperature anomalies shifted the period they stay in breeding sites. Longer stays lead to a decrease in their food source or attracting more predatory species and disrupting the biodiversity balance. Increased heat is shifting the migration pattern more polewards, where non-migratory animals are also moving. This will lead to food scarcity and the introduction of new diseases to which native species are not immune. Disruption in phenological events creates a chain of effects that reduces the abundance of species and increases their vulnerability to extinction (Allcock et al., 2022; Crear et al., 2022; Kanamori et al., 2023; Linssen et al., 2023).

These impacts of climate change have brought wildlife close to human societies, causing human-wildlife conflict. In response to habitat loss and food scarcity, some species have relocated to areas with more favorable environmental conditions, even in close proximity to farmlands, fisheries, and communities. Similarly, humans have moved their livestock to areas with available vegetation that are close to wildlife habitats. Limited natural resources in these areas created human-wildlife conflicts, putting both sides of these conflicts in danger (Santora et al., 2020; Abrahms, 2021; Newsom et al., 2023; Guarnieri et al., 2024). Although, in some areas certain indigenous cultural practices can provide some level of mitigation, it requires conservation strategies and government policies to prevent this issue. However, these policies are often human-centric, or not clear on certain events such as poaching or collisions (IUCN, 2023).

The reviewed literature demonstrates several ways that climate change impacts biodiversity on Earth. While each of these effects seems to disrupt a particular aspect of wildlife, by synthesizing these impacts, a clearer image emerges of how these factors interact to destroy ecosystems and lead to extinction. Some of these effects directly affect the species' existence, while others act indirectly through interaction with their environmental factors. Figure 15 provides a visual summary of these interconnected impacts, drawing from key insights across the studies reviewed. It illustrates the pathways through which climate change influences wildlife, as interpreted from the collective research. Despite the current efforts of scientists and conservationists these impacts of climate change, whether directly or indirectly, are driving species to extinction. Although certain impacts are irreversible, there are limited opportunities to decelerate and reverse the loss of wildlife.

Figure 15. Impacts of Climate Change on Wildlife

Source: Author's creation. Image: Microsoft Office 365.

4.3. Intelligent Machines Serving Wildlife

Environmental and wildlife conservation studies have increasingly utilized statistical and computational models to analyze data, for detecting, tracking, and predicting changes in ecosystems and biodiversity. Substantial amounts of data have been gathered over the past decades that help scientists to understand events leading to climate change and their impact on Earth. Although the introduction of computers provides speed and accuracy for these statistical models, the interpretation of results relies on experts' judgment. Furthermore, utilizing these models requires a certain level of mathematical, statistical, and programming experience, which are time consuming and may not be within everyone's skill set. With increase in real-time data from various observation devices, machine learning models have enabled complex analytical models to be more accessible, while increasing the accuracy of data analysis. Recent advances in artificial intelligence technology have helped to create more artificial intelligence-based solutions for environmental studies, natural sciences, and wildlife conservation. Artificial intelligence has been applied in wildlife monitoring, the development of predictive models for climate and biodiversity changes, detecting wildlife poaching and trafficking, and artificial intelligence-based mitigation strategies, though it is accompanied by certain limitations and ethical challenges.

4.3.1. Common Applications of Artificial Intelligence

Wildlife monitoring technology has been utilizing various sensory devices to collect data from species and their environments. These devices collect images, acoustic and seismic signals, temperature, tri-axial accelerometer data, and GPS locations. Additionally, remote-sensing devices including satellites, unmanned aerial vehicles, and *Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUV)* have been extensively utilized in this field (Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021; Tuia et al., 2022; Rubbens et al., 2023). Community observation reports and data from citizen scientists are also used as another data source for wildlife monitoring (Tuia et al., 2022). Real-time and accurate processing, analyzing, and interpreting these data is crucial for the current state of global climate crisis. Computer technology provides the computation power required for the application of artificial intelligence models to execute these tasks (Pichler & Hartig, 2023; Rubbens et al., 2023).

Different machine learning models are utilized in the conservation field. Convolutional neural networks have shown better results in species detection and identification tasks. These models can be trained with different forms of data to provide autonomous wildlife monitoring for research and conservation projects (Román Ruiz et al., 2023; Batist et al., 2024). The importance of such machine learning models is more evident where there is limited data available on endangered species, as these models can be trained on augmented and synthetic data for the accuracy of their tasks (Brito et al., 2024). The combination of remote sensing and machine learning algorithms proved as an efficient method for detecting anomalies in wildlife's health, habitats, migration patterns, and phenological events. Early detection of diseases using artificial intelligence-based analysis of fauna and flora can help conservationists to prevent the spread of infection. Similarly, in extreme weather, early detection of wildfire or floods can save the lives of organisms. Moreover, autonomous machine learning models can detect deforestation activities or ocean pollution in real-time, by processing aerial and satellite images (Wolf et al., 2020; Hua et al., 2022; Patton et al., 2023; Buchelt et al., 2024; Delplanque et al., 2024).

Understanding communication signals between species is a key factor in wildlife conservation. Machine learning models analyze visual, acoustic, and seismic signals that animals use to communicate, aiming to interpret them as part of automatic monitoring projects (Brickson et al., 2023). This information along with behavioral patterns learned by relevant algorithms can help to create alerts for unnatural events like human intrusion, to detect and stop poachers and hunters. These methods can also detect wildlife proximity to human communities to prevent human-wildlife conflicts (de Knecht et al., 2021; Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021; Tuia et al., 2022).

Tracking wildlife expands outside of their natural habitat to monitor the wildlife trades by poachers and traffickers. Machine learning models monitor online platforms for images and texts that are promoting wildlife sales and can identify species or their parts when presented on the web, to alert legal authorities.

Additionally, images and videos shared on social media platforms by individuals can point to digital and physical markets (Cardoso et al., 2023; Kulkarni & Di Minin, 2023).

While artificial intelligence-based monitoring solutions process data in real-time to track and protect wildlife ecosystems, predicting the changes in these ecosystems is a key factor in optimizing the typically scarce conservation resources. Certain machine learning models such as *Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt)* and *Random Forest (RF)* can provide predictive models for climate change, habitat loss, disease distribution, and species distribution that assist conservationists in their mitigation plans (Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020). Many conservation strategies are created by governments or intergovernmental organizations as part of their broader climate change mitigation and adaptation forecasts (Chen et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence-based algorithms can use multiple variables for predictions to include more scientific factors in such strategies rather than humancentric and political planning. Other aspects of wildlife conservation can also benefit from predictive machine learning models (Scoville et al., 2021; Silvestro et al., 2022). Shifts in phenological events, and migration patterns can be studied by certain algorithms using temporal data and environmental variables (Capinha et al., 2024). Although these tasks may seem to be purely scientific, their results will help to learn natural mitigation and adaptation methods from wildlife to establish more organic strategies for protecting ecosystems (Silva et al., 2022; Castro et al., 2024).

4.3.2. Predominant Machine Learning Models

A crucial factor in successful application of artificial intelligence is selecting the appropriate model for the project. A number of the reviewed studies provided an overview of artificial intelligence and its application in biology and conservation, as well as models commonly utilized in various environmental studies with their application areas (Borowiec et al., 2022; Tuia et al., 2022; Pichler & Hartig, 2023; Rubbens et al., 2023). Although these studies refer to various research fields in ecology and wildlife science, there are certain machine learning models that appear to be employed in all these fields. Furthermore, the experimental research reviewed for this thesis confirmed the common application of certain models for specific types of tasks such as convolutional neural networks for image identification. It was further noted that some of the researchers evaluated multiple models to compare their accuracy and performance in their study subjects (Table 4).

Additionally, while some teams developed a new model for their tasks such as APLASTIC-Q by Wolf et al. (2020) and CAPTAIN by Silvestro et al. (2022), the majority of projects used renowned models (Table 5) and trained them for their specific tasks.

Table 4. Machine Learning Models Used by a Subset of Reviewed Literature

Model	Project Scope	Source
Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)	- Species identification and classification	Wolf et al. (2020), Palmer et al. (2021), Hua et al. (2022), Cardoso et al. (2023), Bothmann et al. (2023), Kulkarni and Di Minin (2023), Patton et al. (2023), Román Ruiz et al. (2023), Delplanque et al. (2024), Brito et al. (2024), Blair et al. (2024), Batist et al. (2024)
Neural Network	- Species distribution model - Extinction risk assessment	Mosebo Fernandes et al. (2020), Silva et al. (2022), Silvestro et al. (2022)
Random Forest	- Species distribution model - Phenological events prediction	Mosebo Fernandes et al. (2020), Capinha et al. (2024), Blair et al. (2024)
Support Vector Machine (SVM)	- Species distribution model	Mosebo Fernandes et al. (2020), de Knecht et al. (2021)
Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM)	- Species distribution model - Phenological events prediction	Kanamori et al. (2023), Blair et al. (2024)
Boosted Regression Tree (BRT)	- Phenological events prediction	Capinha et al. (2024)
Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt)	- Species distribution model	Mosebo Fernandes et al. (2020)
k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN)	- Species identification and classification	Román Ruiz et al. (2023)

Source: Author's creation. Data from reviewed literature.

Neural network algorithms have been used in classification and multi-variable prediction tasks, where they showed effective performance. In the wildlife conservations field, research with a focus on habitat loss prediction, population estimation, decision-making, and risk assessment projects that use structured data can benefit from the performance of these models. (Borowiec et al., 2022; Pichler & Hartig, 2023; Rubbens et al., 2023).

Table 5. Renowned Machine Learning Models

Model Name	First Introduction	Type	First Developed By
k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN)	1951	Instance-Based Learning, Supervised Learning	Fix and Hodges
SVM (Support Vector Machine)	1995	Supervised Learning	Cortes & Vapnik
Random Forest	2001	Decision Tree Ensemble Method	Breiman
MaxEnt (Maximum Entropy)	2004	Statistical Learning	Phillips et al.
AlexNet	2012	Convolutional Neural Network	Krizhevsky et al.
VGG	2014	Convolutional Neural Network	Simonyan and Zisserman
Inception-V3	2015	Convolutional Neural Network	Szegedy et al.
ResNet	2015	Convolutional Neural Network	He et al.
YOLO	2015	Convolutional Neural Network	Redmon et al.
SqueezeNet	2016	Convolutional Neural Network	Iandola et al.
XGBoost	2016	Gradient Boosting Algorithm	Chen et al.
DenseNet	2016	Convolutional Neural Network	Huang et al.
Xception	2016	Convolutional Neural Network	Chollet
LightGBM	2017	Gradient Boosting Algorithm	Ke et al./Microsoft Research
EfficientNet	2019	Convolutional Neural Network	Tan & Le

Renowned models used for image recognition, classification, distribution modeling, and prediction. They were commonly used in reviewed literature. Source: Author's creation. Please see Appendix A for references.

The majority of the studies suggested that convolutional neural networks were the most effective models for species detection and classification projects. Convolutional neural networks have outperformed other machine learning models in image-based identification tasks, by extracting details from images

(Borowiec et al., 2022; Rubbens et al., 2023). Their accuracy in image processing makes them an ideal solution for habitat and species monitoring, and behavioral analysis. Particularly, these models can efficiently use remote sensing data that is gathered non-invasively, like satellite images (Hua et al., 2022; Tuia et al., 2022).

Furthermore, their precision is especially valuable in acoustic classification tasks, where sound signals are visualized by transforming into 2D images and require more precision in feature extraction, which is the key strength of convolutional neural networks (Román Ruiz et al., 2023; Batist et al., 2024). They are also the most suitable models for monitoring wildlife trade on digital platforms such as social media, for the same reason (Cardoso et al., 2023; Kulkarni & Di Minin, 2023). Additionally, the performance of convolutional neural networks improves as more data become available, and when large datasets are not available, data augmentation can produce larger number of images for training purpose. Although there are various pre-trained models available today, each project would require fine-tuning of models with their datasets. This transfer learning step in convolutional neural networks can be achieved with a smaller dataset (Hua et al., 2022). These features have made these models more appealing for researchers, and therefore numerous high-performance models have been developed in recent years and become available to the fields of environmental science and wildlife conservation (Borowiec et al., 2022; Pichler & Hartig, 2023; Rubbens et al., 2023).

While convolutional neural networks are the ideal models for image processing, their complexity makes them less preferred for prediction and assessment tasks. It was observed that Random Forest (RF) model performed well in species distribution model and prediction tasks, even in studies where similar datasets were used for comparison between various models (Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020; Capinha et al., 2024). Random forest is a *Decision Tree-based* model that has fewer hyperparameters than neural networks, which makes it easier to use. This model is more resistant to overfitting and can handle noisy data or missing data points, with limited impact on the results. Furthermore, since this model combines the results from multiple decision trees, the prediction performance and accuracy of the results are higher. Additionally, in this model it is easier to determine the important variables of the model. Although this model is utilized in classification and regression tasks, it is recommended for its performance for species richness prediction, because of its capability to prioritize the variables for decision-making (Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020; Rubbens et al., 2023; Capinha et al., 2024). Other commonly used models that employ decision trees are *Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)*, and *Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)*. These models have demonstrated a high performance (accuracy) with complex patterns, particularly handling noise, and missing data similar to random forest. However, their complexity, sensitivity to tuning, and their longer computation time due to sequential computing, have made them less easy to employ (Kanamori et al., 2023; Pichler & Hartig, 2023).

The machine learning model that is widely used in species distribution models is Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt), a probabilistic model that uses the species presence data in a defined location, to predict the probability of their future presence in that area. This model can consider environmental variables in prediction, which makes it a fitting model to study the impacts of climate change on species distribution and habitat loss (Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020; Branco et al., 2023). Another classification model that is often used in biology and conservation, *Support Vector Machine (SVM)* is a supervised learning classifier with the ability to separate labeled data into binary classes based on the best hyperplane (separation line). This model is used as classifier for high-dimensional datasets (datasets with many features) in ecology and environmental science, for its accuracy and efficiency (de Knegt et al., 2021; Pichler & Hartig, 2023; Buchelt et al., 2024). A simple classifier that can be used with small datasets, is *k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN)*. It is a supervised learning model that classifies data points based on their proximity to “k” neighbors. Since this model goes through all data points, it is usually recommended for small datasets to avoid long computation time (Román Ruiz et al., 2023; Rubbens et al., 2023).

4.3.3. Biodiversity Data Sources

Every new machine learning algorithm must be trained on the data that is related to its task. Larger datasets in training step help the model to reach higher accuracy in its results. It was noted that the majority of renown convolutional neural network models used for image recognition were pretrained on *ImageNet* database, which is used as reference for performance of algorithms on processing its image datasets. These models were retrained and fine-tuned with project-specific datasets. Moreover, specific projects developed their custom model and trained them with data collected for their research subjects (Wolf et al., 2020; Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022).

Over decades, vast amounts of data have been gathered in various fields of environmental and biological studies, which can be used for training models. Several databases such as Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and *iNaturalist* provide access to a variety of datasets from various aspects of wildlife conservation studies (Table 6). These databases have collected data from various sources, including digitizing the historical and manually gathered samples, or crowdsourcing with the help of citizen science projects. Moreover, there are specialized data sources that focus on biodiversity and ecosystem in particular areas as part of special projects such as *LandKlif*, which is a regional research platform by the *University of Würzburg* and *The Bavarian Climate Research Network* (Bothmann et al., 2023; *LandKlif Project Homepage*, n.d.). While some projects utilized publicly available data, other researchers collected new data from the field by utilizing wildlife monitoring devices and retrained certain models with that collected data for their particular tasks (Wolf et al., 2020; Delplanque et al., 2024; Batist

et al., 2024; de Knecht et al., 2021). Certain teams created projects on crowdsourcing platforms such as *Zooniverse* to obtain large amounts of data from a wider geographic area (Palmer et al., 2021).

Table 6. Data Platforms Used by a Subset of Reviewed Literature

Database	Type	Source
COCO	Large-scale crowdsourced image database	https://cocodataset.org/#home
FathomNet	Marine habitat and species crowdsourced database	https://fathomnet.org/fathomnet/#/
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	Global biodiversity data aggregator	https://www.gbif.org/
GlobalTreeSearch	Plant species data aggregator	https://tools.bgci.org/global_tree_search.php
Happywhale	Whale sighting crowdsourced database	https://happywhale.com/home
ImageNet	Large-scale crowdsourced image database	https://www.image-net.org/
iNaturalist	Citizen science platform for wildlife observation	https://www.inaturalist.org/
IUCN Red List of Threatened Species	Global biodiversity conservation status data aggregator	https://www.iucnredlist.org/
Kaggle	Machine learning models and crowdsourced data platform	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets
Mushroom Observer	Fungi species crowdsourced data	https://mushroomobserver.org/
Zooniverse	Citizen science platform for scientific observation	https://www.zooniverse.org/

Renowned data sources used for image recognition research, which were commonly used in reviewed literature. Source: Author’s creation. Data from reviewed literature.

As presented in Table 6, biodiversity data sources were introduced and utilized by reviewed literatures can be *Aggregators* or *Crowdsources*. Aggregator databases supply centralized, standard, and organized datasets as a result of their data verification process. They gather scientific data from reputable research institutes and other formal sources that have data verification protocols. Therefore, users can expect to access reliable, high quality, and scientifically verified data on these sources

(Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022). In contrast, citizen science and crowdsourced datasets may vary in quality, unless the platform has a data verification process to confirm the accuracy of the data (Palmer et al., 2021; Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022). However, these sources can provide access to a large volume of data from diverse geographical areas that can expand the analysis (Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021; Tuia et al., 2022). Furthermore, these platforms have projects with real-time data that can enhance the conservation monitoring solutions (Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022; Sterner et al., 2023).

4.3.4. Artificial Intelligence in Action

The rapid disruption of ecosystems due to climate change has severe impacts on wildlife and their habitats, creating the need for innovative strategies to reduce these impacts, protect the remaining of biodiversity, and restore ecosystem stability (see Section 3.2.1). Artificial intelligence plays a crucial role in various aspects of wildlife conservation, and habitat restoration planning. It transforms how scientists, conservationists and decision-makers respond proactively to continuous changes in environmental elements. Artificial intelligence models enhance the speed, accuracy, and effectiveness of data-driven decisions to reduce the impacts of climate change on wildlife. As described in Section 3.2.2, artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation can be applied in various activities, and the interrelation of these tasks provides solutions to mitigate the impacts of climate change in wildlife and develop efficient conservation and restoration plans.

Data is the essential requirement for any artificial intelligence-based solution. Ecosystem and biodiversity data are collected through various monitoring devices including advanced remote-sensing technologies such as satellites, and unmanned aerial and underwater vehicles. Additionally, a large amount of data has become available through community observations and crowdsourcing projects (Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021; Tuia et al., 2022). Artificial intelligence models that are designed for object detection and classification are employed to analyze these monitoring data and provide multiple forms of results based on their objectives. The primary objective of artificial intelligence models utilized in wildlife monitoring is to have real-time awareness of the species and their habitats to detect any unusual changes in their behavior, health, or surrounding environment. Artificial intelligence-based monitoring systems specifically play a crucial role in the protection of endangered species by tracking human activities around their habitats (Brito et al., 2024). Additionally, certain artificial intelligence models can be trained to detect intrusion of poachers in real-time and take protective measures to stop them (de Knecht et al., 2021; Hua et al., 2022). Furthermore, machine learning monitoring algorithms track wildlife trades on various markets and alert law enforcement agencies in real-time (Cardoso et al., 2023; Kulkarni & Di Minin, 2023).

While protecting wildlife and conservation areas, certain algorithms provide various analysis of the collected data to recognize patterns in species' behavior, or changes in environmental elements of conservation area. The objective of these algorithms is to draw a picture of the existing distribution of diverse species of fauna and flora in the monitored area and develop a predictive model of what it may look like in the future (Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020; Tuia et al., 2022). These predictive models can further evaluate the potential sources of threats to biodiversity of conservation areas and conduct extinction risk assessment on species (Silva et al., 2022). Analysis of satellite and aerial data through machine learning algorithms provides a complete picture of species abundance, habitat structure and any environmental disruptions, which assists such studies. Similarly, in marine conservation efforts, machine learning algorithms monitor changes in aquatic environment (e.g., coral reefs), track species abundance, detect poaching and illegal fishing, and identify pollution (Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021; Rubbens et al., 2023).

Species distribution models can provide key insights into the relationship between species and environmental factors, including climate change, and how they response to changes in these factors. Thus, the application of machine learning algorithms in species distribution models brings the capability of analyzing extensive data for study areas to create a prediction model of how each factor can impact the distribution of species. As a result, specific approaches can be designed for each conservation zone to ensure effectiveness in mitigation plans and efficiency in resources utilization (Mosebo Fernandes et al., 2020; Silvestro et al., 2022).

An important case is utilization of machine learning models in forest monitoring and management, which has an impact on terrestrial, aerial, and soil biodiversity. These models provide visual representation of vegetation, animals, and other organisms in the monitored areas through analysis of temporal and real-time datasets (Buchelt et al., 2024). While monitoring models detect environmental changes such as plant diseases, wildfires, and deforestation, other machine learning models can simulate multiple future scenarios based on these datasets and given variables, to predict the possible changes due to various factor, including climate change (Liu et al., 2021; Silvestro et al., 2022). These predictions assist experts and decision-makers to plan for protection and restoration of plant species that are habitats and food sources for other organisms in the forests (Liu et al., 2021; Buchelt et al., 2024). Machine learning models enable precision in analysis of ecosystem and environmental conditions like soil type, which increase the effectiveness of seeding and planting (Figure 16). The result of such models can be used by other models to plan automated seeding and nursing processes by utilizing unmanned vehicles for precise and cost-effective forest management (Castro et al., 2024).

Figure 16. Automated Precise Seeding with Drones and Artificial Intelligence

Sample workflow to implement artificial intelligence for precision seeding. This solution will improve the accuracy and efficiency of forest restoration efforts. Source: Castro et al. (2024, fig. 2)

Phenological events in wildlife have been shifted due to climate change (see Section 4.2). These events include reproduction, hibernation, and migration that are crucial to survival of species and biodiversity of Earth. Machine learning models can detect the changes in these events due to various environmental factors, through temporal and spatial monitoring data, and create a predictive model of their future state

in various climate change scenarios (Kanamori et al., 2023; Buchelt et al., 2024). These models assist conservation experts to plan for new conservation areas, or necessary intervention to protect species through reproduction in conservation sites.

Seasonal migration is an important life event for migratory species to travel between breeding sites and winter living areas. As climate change has affected the temperature and length of seasons, data shows shift in time and geography of migration patterns. Machine learning algorithms enable scientists to study the impact of environmental drivers on the movement of this species. Furthermore, researchers create prediction machine learning models that can explain how these factors can potentially change migration patterns. These studies are vital in implementing effective conservation plans, specifically for vulnerable and endangered species, to protect them through their migration paths and in their seasonal living locations (Chambault et al., 2021; Rubbens et al., 2023; Guarnieri et al., 2024).

In response to climate change and its impacts, certain species have changed various aspects of their life to adapt to the new climate and environmental conditions. Machine learning algorithms for species distribution models can show how climatic conditions have influenced species' way of life to survive the effects of such changes. Understanding natural mitigation methods can provide a view on how conservation efforts should be directed to provide support and protection for species with the goal of minimizing human interference in the process of natural adaptation and healing process in certain ecosystems (Carbeck et al, 2022).

Implementation of various artificial intelligence solutions can help wildlife through protective measures, reproduction plans, and habitat restoration, which can further help to reduce human-wildlife conflicts. Automated monitoring and alerting systems utilizing artificial intelligence can detect and inform authorities in real-time as a preventive method. Machine learning models can describe the distribution of species and human communities to show the conflict zones, helping experts to implement protective measures for both sides of the conflicts. Moreover, some conflicts are seasonal in certain areas due to migration paths intersecting human communities. Machine learning models that predict migration patterns and their future changes under the influence of climate, can help conservationists to develop mitigation plans such as creating migration corridors, to prevent these conflicts (Brickson et al., 2023; Guarnieri et al., 2024).

An effective conservation and restoration solution to protect global biodiversity demands a structured approach that integrates various artificial intelligence-powered tools capable of sharing data, analysis, and predictions to enable efficient planning and implementation of climate change mitigation strategies in wildlife conservation. A suggested framework for the integration of various artificial intelligence-powered solutions is illustrated in Figure 17. This diagram demonstrates how the individual artificial

intelligence-powered solutions described in this section can be integrated to form a unified and effective conservation solution.

Figure 17. Artificial Intelligence in Action

The interrelation between artificial intelligence-based solutions to mitigate the impacts of climate change on wildlife. Source: Author’s creation. Image: Microsoft Office 365.

4.4. Implications

Although today climate change studies prioritize its environmental impact in relation to humans and social, economic, and political aspects of their lives, scientific society and conservationist organizations continue their efforts to understand the impacts of drastic changes in the climate on biodiversity and how they can help nature to reduce these impacts on ecosystems and wildlife. With some of these impacts are irreversible, technological advances provide more sophisticated tools that assist scientists and conservationists to accelerate their data analysis to reach solutions. This research has found valuable applications of artificial intelligence in studies of climate change, its impact on wildlife, and wildlife conservation projects.

- During the life of planet Earth several climatic events occurred, which led to the extinction of certain organisms and evolution of new species. The current climate change is driven by human activities over past centuries and continues to be a serious threat to the biodiversity of Earth. Wildlife has been impacted by climate change through extreme weather, habitat loss, and phenological disruption. Human activities have exacerbated these impacts by increasing emissions, habitat disruption, and poaching. Habitat loss has decreased the proximity between humans and wildlife, creating human-wildlife conflicts in search of access to natural resources and food. Direct and indirect impacts of climate change have driven certain species to extinction and many others are at significant risk of extinction.
- In many countries wildlife protection policies and strategies are decades old and cannot provide the level of action required at the current state of global climate and environmental crisis. Climate change mitigation strategists can use multi-variable predictive machine learning models to assist decision-makers with developing practical ecosystem-centric policies for wildlife conservation projects by adding environmental factors into their forecasts.
- Conservation projects require scientific foundation on understanding environment, species, their habitat, and their distribution model in the conservation areas. Machine learning models can predict environmental and habitat changes under climate effects that will impact the distribution of species in those areas. This knowledge prepares experts to plan ahead for actions.
- Monitoring the wildlife and conservation areas, which are mostly located in low-income countries, requires financial and human resources that are difficult to access. Moreover, there is the risk of physical encounters with animals or poachers that can put the life of members in danger. Artificial intelligence shows potential for significantly improving real-time monitoring of wildlife and their habitats. Machine learning models with object recognition algorithms process data collected by various remote-sensing devices (e.g., camera traps, unmanned aerial or underwater vehicles, and acoustic recorders) to observe the environmental changes, movements of animals, or detect human intrusions. These models can reduce the need for invasive methods for data collection, which are complicated, costly, and require substantial resources.
- By using data collected by monitoring solutions, machine learning models can study animals' behavior and communications, which help with tracking their movements and migration patterns as a protective measure for endangered species.
- Tracking phenological patterns of fauna and flora can indicate any disruption in their life events, which is crucial to survival of many species and ecosystems. Predictive machine learning models

are employed to understand and follow these events by considering multiple environmental variables.

- Outside of conservation areas, machine learning models monitor wildlife trading markets on various platforms to detect trades and alert authorities. These solutions in combination with poacher detection alerts in conservation areas will reduce the loss of species to poaching.
- The complexity, cost, and ethical constraints associated with artificial intelligence models are obstacles in application of responsible artificial intelligence in scientific fields including wildlife conservation.
- Decentralized species databases, quality of certain data sources, and misalignment of species classifications between various databases used for training machine learning models, introducing noise, bias, and inaccurate predictions. Additionally, data security is a vital factor in wildlife conservation to prevent poachers accessing data that can compromise the security of wildlife, conservation areas, and people who work in those areas.

Nevertheless, applications of artificial intelligence in this field have their limitations and complications, which researchers continue to improve their models and solutions to resolve, or at a very least minimize their impact of existing issues.

4.5. Limitations

4.5.1. Limitations of Research Method

Transferred bias, the common weakness of scientific research, may have potentially affected the methodology utilized in this thesis as well. The data or results published in the reviewed literature or organizational reports may be biased, which can be difficult to detect. As an example, many practical experiments with machine learning methods used similar data sources such as Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) or iNaturalist, which may increase the possibility of bias in their results. It was observed that several publications, except those concluded from field and practical research, are based on the theoretical reviews of previous works that can increase the likelihood of bias, noise, or error propagation. An example of such noise was found in a paper published in 2022. It referred to the 1896 paper from Svante Arrhenius (1859–1927) as the first global warming prediction, but the paper they referenced solely concluded that fossil fuels are a source of carbon dioxide (Arrhenius, 1896). Therefore, selected resources required a detailed examination to minimize the errors.

The university library had limited access to literature in biology and environmental science. In some instances that databases required access through academic institutions, IU University of Applied

Sciences was not listed, or did not have access to certain literature. Additionally, the use of artificial intelligence in this field is still relatively new, which results in limited diversity in research subjects. Thus, studies have generated limited data and where institutions possess quality data, they are not available to all universities. Consequently, search tools directed to a limited number of literature with the most common applications of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation.

This literature review was designed to concentrate on climate change mitigation solutions with a wildlife-centric approach to understand the impacts of climate change on wildlife and how artificial intelligence may be able to help with reducing these impacts. Therefore, this review may have potential for selection bias, resulting from the design goal and further by the subject of acquired studies that examined commonly recognized applications of artificial intelligence in the field of wildlife conservation.

4.5.2. Artificial Intelligence Application Boundaries

Technological advancements, particularly the recent increase in artificial intelligence solutions, are enhancing scientific research, however the cost of these solutions is still high. The primary cost of machine learning solutions is the cost of training the models. This phase, particularly for training convolutional neural networks for image processing, requires high computational power for long hours, which increases with the complexity of model and data volume. Although many scientific institutes have access to required hardware or cloud services for this task, it remains an expensive phase of project for small organizations or individuals without that access to such computational power (Borowiec et al., 2022; Hua et al., 2022; Tuia et al., 2022; Pichler & Hartig, 2023; Rubbens et al., 2023). Therefore, the majority of reviewed studies utilized pretrained ready-to-use models and used transfer learning to fine-tune them with the data from their projects. Although these projects provided real-life solutions using available models and data, conservation organizations required more complex, reliable, and accurate solutions for wildlife monitoring and intrusion detection tasks. Employing sophisticated models can be costly, particularly for conservation organizations with budget constraints (Hua et al., 2022; Tuia et al., 2022).

Artificial intelligence prediction models that will be used for climate change mitigation strategies and conservation planning by government and intergovernmental organizations must be more sophisticated to minimize error and bias, while providing the highest possible accuracy. Therefore, the cost of designing and training such customized models can impact their budget. It was estimated that the training cost for two major artificial intelligence models, GPT-4 (OpenAI) and Gemini Ultra (Google), in 2023 was \$78 million and \$191 million, respectively (Maslej et al., 2024). Commonly, creating state-of-

the-art artificial intelligence models is more feasible for industry than academia, due to significant financial and technological resource requirements (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Number of Notable Machine Learning Models by Sector, 2003-2023

Source: Author's creation. Data source: The AI Index 2024 Annual Report (Maslej et al., 2024).

Comparably, countries with more technological and financial resources (Figure 19) are developing more notable artificial intelligence models than the rest of the world (Maslej et al., 2024).

Figure 19. Number of Notable Machine Learning Models by Geographical Area, 2023

Source: Author's creation. Data source: The AI Index 2024 Annual Report (Maslej et al., 2024).

In addition to the cost associated with training step, access to high-quality and relevant training data can be challenging. Furthermore, certain models require labeling data that extends the timeline, resulting in additional cost of manual tasks and potential for errors.

There are several pretrained models available at relatively low cost for research projects, but they require programming skills such as Python to retrain them for the tasks in hand. Many researchers may have some levels of computer programming knowledge, but for complex code changes they may require collaboration of an expert programmer for their projects, specifically if they propose a new algorithm, which can affect their budget. Additionally, involvement of artificial intelligence experts in data collection and preparation may be required for certain projects that can increase the cost of those projects. Moreover, the application of these solutions in the field relies on artificial intelligence experts for transfer learning and customizing them, frequent performance monitoring, and impact assessment (Tuia et al., 2022; Brickson et al., 2023; Kulkarni & Di Minin, 2023).

The intricacy of machine learning models leads to difficulty in interpreting their predictions, particularly in deep learning models with complex architectures, which frames them as a black box. The complexity of these machine learning models presents scientific and ethical concerns as there is no transparency in how a model is trained or arrives at a prediction, and it is difficult to understand what they have learned (Nandutu et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022; Pichler & Hartig, 2023; Rubbens et al., 2023).

4.5.3. Data Credibility

A key to a successful artificial intelligence-based solution is a well-trained machine learning model, and this can be achieved with access to appropriate datasets that are systematically curated and relevant. As discussed in Section 4.3.3, various biodiversity data sources are available that provide various levels of quality, geographical coverage, and species diversity. While some datasets are gathered through formal scientific methods, others are the result of citizen science projects and amateur enthusiasts. Nevertheless, both types of databases have their weaknesses.

Global data aggregators have procedures to confirm the accuracy and quality of data, which they preferably acquired from scientific institutes or official government organizations. The lengthy process of data validation leads to limited up-to-date data in these databases (Sternier et al., 2023). Furthermore, these databases filter data based on the subjects that fit their objectives, which contributes to their data limitations. Data available on these databases may cover only certain geographical areas or limited categories of species, leading to sampling bias (Borowiec, et al., 2021). Conversely, crowdsources databases have less restrictions on data validation, which can impact the quality and accuracy of obtained data. Lack of quality assurance in some of these sources can lead to noisy, biased, false data

points, and consequently pseudoscience, which will impact biodiversity and conservation decisions (Galaz et al., 2021; Nandutu et al., 2021; Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022).

Decentralization is the common limitation for both types of data sources. This problem causes misalignment of data structures, classification of species, search indexes, and policies, which make data collection processes open to noise and error (Sterner et al., 2023). Additionally, there is an imbalance in the biodiversity datasets currently available. The amount of available data on species depends on their abundance and frequency of observations, as well as geographical locations (Rubbens et al., 2023). Therefore, there are fewer or no datasets available for certain classes of species than others, particularly rare species with limited presence. These data limitations directly impact the accuracy of machine learning models through training, resulting in bias and lack of generalization in algorithms (Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022; Borowiec et al., 2022).

Problems associated with training data can not only lead to technical failure of machine learning models, they also can impact the future of wildlife conservation by inaccurate predictions and decision-making.

4.5.4. Artificial Intelligence Ethics: Logical Tightrope

Regardless of the origin of studies, the existing literature emphasizes the importance of ethics in utilizing artificial intelligence (Ethical AI) in wildlife research and conservation. Main issue with artificial intelligence-based solution is bias that can severely impact the wildlife studies and conservation plans (Covles et al., 2021; Galaz et al., 2021; Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022). Although this issue is initiated by the technical process, experts consider it a crucial ethical issue because it can lead to social and environmental consequences that put the life of species and people who protect them at risk (Nandutu et al., 2021; Scoville et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022). Poor data quality, outdated data, limited environmental samples, and human errors (or intentions) in labeling, are main sources of bias in training datasets (Borowiec et al., 2022). Data conversion methods like voice-to-image conversion can also create noise or reduce the quality of the output data. When biased datasets are used to train machine learning models, it will lead to unintended algorithm bias. Furthermore, models will amplify the bias and therefore, such models are likely to provide skewed predictions or misidentify species. Additionally, the type of variables that are considered in algorithm design methods may introduce unintended bias. Another concern is intentional algorithm bias that can be introduced in models design for certain gains. Regardless of the sources, this bias will spread through transfer learning to other solutions as a variable of the algorithm (Galaz et al., 2021; Luccioni & Rolnick, 2022; Pichler & Hartig, 2023).

Part of wildlife conservation is the security of ecosystems and conservation teams. Thus, data security is another crucial factor in this field. Technological advances are available to criminals as well as other

users. They can access wildlife data from collecting points by hacking into sensing devices, or physical access to devices with recording history. Furthermore, data transfer and storage can be similarly vulnerable to hacking. Additionally, access to data requires policies to prevent poachers and traffickers from acquiring information that helps them to bridge the security of conservation areas, their ecosystems, and the operational teams (Nandutu et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022). While certain data sources that provide more detailed and live data demand a form of authentication (e.g., academic, governmental, or organizational), there are numerous data sources with free public access and relatively accurate information that can be used by individuals with any intention. This problem, similar to data and algorithm bias, is a technical challenge with ethical consequences.

Machine learning solutions demand high computation power, particularly in training phase, for faster processing time. This requires employing advanced hardware and higher energy consumption. The process of manufacturing, installation, and running the hardware can contribute to carbon emissions. A number of works suggested that strategists should consider this emission resulting from utilizing artificial intelligence solutions in climate change mitigation and wildlife conservation planning (Cowls et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022).

4.6. Outlook

In the future, the role of artificial intelligence in climate change mitigation activities and wildlife conservation is anticipated to grow as technological advancements continue to evolve and global environmental challenges become worse. Notable patterns suggest that artificial intelligence will play a critical role in this field, especially improving climate impact predictions, species monitoring and protection, habitat restoration, and decision-making. However, there are technical and ethical considerations that need to be addressed to achieve responsible artificial intelligence to successfully implement in conservation efforts.

4.6.1. Future Artificial Intelligence Trends in Conservation

Artificial intelligence technologies are expected to become more sophisticated, precise, and integrated with real-time data. These advancements, particularly in predictive models and ecosystem monitoring, will transform how scientists and conservationists respond to environmental disruptions. Advanced artificial intelligence models will also play a crucial role in proactive and data-driven decision-making, with including environmental variables in their algorithms.

The capacity of artificial intelligence models to analyze vast amounts of ecological data in real-time can lead to solutions for reducing the species extinction rates and accelerating the process of ecosystem restoration.

Artificial intelligence may automate the wildlife monitoring tasks and data analysis required for species protection, which will significantly enhance the efficiency of conservation efforts with minimal resources. Autonomous unmanned vehicles equipped with edge computers and machine learning models can monitor conservation areas to detect changes in environmental patterns or identify threats to alert experts. These devices will particularly operate in inaccessible areas without human interference, utilizing artificial intelligence precision.

Machine learning models are expected to assist experts to connect scattered biodiversity databases, organize datasets, unify species data classifications, and create automated data verification methods. These unified databases can ensure the quality and accuracy of data, and equal access to scientific communities and conservation experts to develop and improve machine learning models with high performance for wildlife conservation efforts.

However, achieving these advantages depends on global collaboration for fair access to artificial intelligence technologies, particularly for regions that may not have the required resources to develop or implement these solutions.

4.6.2. Challenges Remain

Future development of artificial intelligence solutions will face certain challenges. The high cost of technology can continue to limit access to advanced solutions for low-income countries. Additionally, political factors can impact the development and access to artificial intelligence solutions.

Complexity of machine learning algorithms, particularly neural networks, will increase as more computational power becomes available. Artificial intelligence experts and environmental scientists will need to continue their collaboration to resolve the ambiguity and interpretation problems associated with sophisticated models.

Data scarcity, specifically limited data on rare and endangered species, can impact development and training algorithm for conservation decisions and efforts. Despite the efforts, data quality and accuracy can stay a limiting factor for achieving accurate predictive models.

Technological advances will be available to the public, including poachers and traffickers. Thus, their ability to access wildlife data and artificial intelligence-based solutions will be a continuous challenge for experts and policymakers.

Certain ethical issues will continue to be associated with artificial intelligence and conservation efforts. Ethical artificial intelligence models that are free from noise and bias will not be achievable, except with global commitment to utilize diverse and verified data, and independence of artificial intelligence models from financial and political manipulations. Additionally, the ethical concerns regarding wildlife surveillance solutions, particularly in the vicinity of human communities, will remain a central issue in policy debates.

4.6.3. Future Research Opportunities

The severity of climate change's impacts on biodiversity calls for more innovative solutions. This thesis suggests collaborative projects between applied sciences universities and scientific institutes in wildlife studies and conservation, to explore various applications of artificial intelligence in this field. These projects can be created as new subjects in certain courses, course projects, or thesis.

Studies experimented with machine learning models have a consensus on the limitation of reliable data. A necessary work is centralizing, organizing, classifying and verifying available data for each conservation area. This task requires collaboration of artificial intelligence scientists, data scientists, ecologists, and conservationists to combine available data from various research and conservation projects and create local databases. Such projects can be the first step in creating a global united database for biodiversity.

Collective, organized research by a group of scientific institutes can evaluate various ready-to-use machine learning models for their accuracy and performance, to identify the most reliable models for wildlife studies and conservation tasks. Such studies can reduce the error in the result of artificial intelligence-based research, caused by utilizing various models on a similar subject. However, these projects must consider the potential bias in selected models, to avoid transferred bias in their future applications.

Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) has been the subject of studies in the field of artificial intelligence in recent years. There is limited research on practical application of these systems in environmental studies, specifically wildlife conservation. Since the most common machine learning methods used for this field are based on neural networks, the power of clarity that explainable artificial intelligence brings in for prediction and decision-making is undeniable. Given the need to expedite studies and actions in wildlife conservation, explainable artificial intelligence is an important subject for future research in application of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation, and climate change mitigation strategies.

Edge computers are advancing as powerful, low-cost devices with small footprints. They can execute programs and process data in real-time on autonomous devices. There are few studies in wildlife

conservation that utilized and examined such efficient hardware in combination with artificial intelligence models. Application of artificial intelligence-based solutions in wildlife can benefit from more research on employing such computers in various remote-sensing devices, particularly real-time monitoring in inaccessible areas. Future research on such solutions can present cost-effective protection and management solutions fitting the limited resources of wildlife conservation organizations.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Summary

Biodiversity on Earth is threatened by anthropogenic climate change and scientists believe the impacts of this disruption are driving species towards mass extinction. The International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species data in 2024 indicates there are 47,141 documented species at risk of extinction, while 1,033 known species are extinct (IUCN, 2024). The velocity of ecosystem disruption and wildlife extinction demands fast responses from scientists, policymakers, and human communities. This necessitates real-time situational awareness of climate and ecosystem changes, and continuous data collection and analysis. Technological advances in computer science have turned artificial intelligence from a concept in the 1950s into a widely accessible solution supporting various scientific fields in the 21st century. In climate change studies, machine learning models can perform data analysis with high accuracy to identify anomalies or provide predictions for environmental shifts and portray their impacts on ecosystems. In the field of wildlife conservation, artificial intelligence can track species, monitor habitats, learn from the natural patterns of ecosystems, and project the future of biodiversity under the effects of climate change. Although the ethical implications and technological cost of such solutions are limiting their applications, with technological advances they may become more accessible to conservationists and benefit wildlife. Despite the fact that it is too late to reverse impacts of climate change, the application of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation can help to protect the remaining natural ecosystems and reduce the extinction rate of remaining species.

5.2. Answering Research Questions

This study examined the current state of climate change, its impact on wildlife, and what are the current applications of artificial intelligence to study and reduce these impacts on ecosystems. The result of this review provides the answers to the thesis questions.

- **What are the key impacts of climate change on wildlife and their habitats?**

Increase in the global temperature, extreme weather, droughts, and decline in ice sheets, has caused geographical shifts and loss of habitats and food sources for many organisms. Many species of animals had to migrate to new areas closer to humans, which has caused human-wildlife conflicts over using natural resources. Rising temperature and change in habitats have increased the vulnerability of species and contributed to higher rate of disease transmission. Furthermore, the phenology of wildlife that follows the seasonal changes is altered and shifted the migration timing in migratory species. This phenological alteration along with temperature increase affected the reproduction system, followed by

a reduction in the abundance of species. These impacts have caused the extinction of many species and threatened the life of many other species.

- **What artificial intelligence technologies are used in wildlife monitoring and data collection?**

Wildlife monitoring aims to track, study, and protect species. Data is gathered by various ecosystem surveillance methods such as fixed or mobile sensors, as well as airborne and underwater remote-sensing devices. Deep neural network models, including Convolutional Neural Networks, analyze this data to track the movement of species, detect disruptions in their habitats, observe changes in their behavior, monitor their health, and identify human intrusion in conservation areas. Autonomous unmanned aerial and underwater vehicles guided by machine learning models are becoming cost-effective monitoring solutions, especially in inaccessible areas. Furthermore, convolutional neural networks detection and classification methods help law enforcements in monitoring digital platforms for illegal wildlife trades. Similar models are also monitoring social media and volunteering platforms as additional data sources for biodiversity monitoring. Predictive machine learning models use the collected environmental data to project a picture of habitat transformation, and species distribution patterns under effects of climate change.

- **What Artificial intelligence-based predictive models are used for forecasting climate impacts on wildlife?**

Artificial intelligence models commonly applied for predictions in wildlife conservation include Random Forest (classification and species distribution modeling), Support Vector Machines (classification), and Maximum Entropy (species distribution modeling). These models are utilized to simulate scenarios based on the available environmental data. They assist with predicting climatic events, which with other environmental variables, would indicate habitat loss, species distribution models and population changes. Furthermore, such models can identify the potential for disease spread in ecosystems based on climate and ecosystem data. Additionally, they can assess other threats to wildlife, identify the species at risk, and their extinction likelihood. Moreover, machine learning algorithms monitor, detect, and predict changes in phenological events and shifts in migration patterns, which directly impact health and abundance of species. Along with decision-making models, they assist policymakers to set effective and efficient conservation strategies.

- **What are the roles of artificial intelligence in habitat restoration and conservation planning?**

Application of artificial intelligence in wildlife conservation starts with monitoring ecosystems to gather and analyze data from all aspects of species' lives. Machine learning models can simulate and predict possible changes in their habitat and life events. These assessments provide a complete picture of how the future would look like for wildlife. Machine learning models can optimize conservation strategies based on various environmental variables. These models can assist in enhancing conservation site selection, monitoring and combating poaching and trafficking, preventing deforestation, preventing and detecting wildfires, detecting pollution, and managing human-wildlife conflicts. Moreover, artificial intelligence can be used to manage data collected by citizen science platforms, to improve quality and availability of data for researchers and conservation organizations. While these applications of artificial intelligence assist experts in specific fields of environmental studies and conservation, a successful conservation solution requires integrating various artificial intelligence tools to develop a comprehensive mitigation and restoration framework, utilizing the technology's full potential in this crucial task.

- **What are the challenges and ethical considerations in using artificial intelligence for wildlife conservation?**

Artificial intelligence accompanies ethical concerns, technological complexity, and application cost. These factors will be transferred to any field that utilizes artificial intelligence-based solutions. Wildlife conservation sites are naturally located in areas that suffer from financial constraints and limited access to current advanced technologies. These limitations are delaying access to full capacity of artificial intelligence in conservation planning and activities. Thus, studies that utilize machine learning models are mostly conducted by universities in wealthier countries, such as those in Europe, North America, Australia, and China. Moreover, most high-performance artificial intelligence solutions are owned by private companies that primarily seek business and financial gains. They control the algorithms and model training, which can be altered by the influence of business or power. Additionally, unprofessional data collection can introduce noise and bias in datasets that will be transferred to the machine learning models as variables for their tasks. Moreover, lack of a united and high-quality database reduces the accuracy of applied artificial intelligence solutions, as researchers that use different datasets may observe different results on a comparable subject. In addition, some open-access datasets can compromise the security of wildlife, conservation areas, and those who work there, by sharing data with poachers and traffickers.

5.3. Recommendations

This research review has provided a view of what solutions have been proposed by experts, and how some of them have been implemented and become available to the field of wildlife conservation. Here, a few solutions are recommended based on the results of this study.

5.3.1. What Can Humans Do Better?

The first and most major step is to make climate change a priority for all nations, governments and leaders. Global summits that their influential members attend by flying on personal aircraft, do not imply the critical situation of climate change.

Climate change mitigation policies are human-centric and impacts on wildlife are viewed as a marginal issue. Wildlife conservation needs ecosystem-centric strategies, policies, and decisions that involve scientists and experts who are interacting with its daily issues.

Policies, procedures, and laws of countries, particularly in countries with significant wildlife abundance, need to be reviewed and updated to align with the realities of the current century and severity of climate crisis. These changes must respect their culture and traditions, to the extent that they do not harm the environment.

Social and cultural awareness regarding the importance of wildlife is as crucial as the efforts of scientists and conservationists. Sharing facts and data in simple words that can be understood by community members, can show how biodiversity on Earth is vital for the survival of humans. Involving indigenous communities to include their knowledge and relationship with nature can also provide a new aspect of wildlife conservation to experts.

The lives of humans around the world depend on the survival of all species. Although the major conservation sites and protected geographical regions are located in low-income countries, preservation of these areas is vital for all countries. Therefore, economically advanced nations, particularly industrial countries that exacerbate the climate crisis, must contribute to the resources required to maintain the protection of these regions and their wildlife population.

5.3.2. How Can Intelligent Machines Be Utilized Better?

As discussed in previous chapters, artificial intelligence models have been utilized only in certain areas of wildlife conservation. As part of a broader effort for saving the remaining of biodiversity there are

some opportunities that will improve the climate change mitigation efforts while protecting the environment and wildlife.

Clean energy is a climate change strategy that is increasing all over the world, without fully examining their impact on wildlife. Wind turbines are one of the common sources of clean energy, but they impact wildlife by causing bird collisions with blades or power lines (onshore turbines), and noise frequencies that distract and confuse marine species (offshore turbines). Furthermore, the construction of turbines and their required utilities cause habitat loss and introduce invasive alien species to the area (Shah et al., 2024). This thesis proposes that by utilizing multi-variable machine learning models for site surveys, projects can predict the long-term shift in the movement and migration patterns of local and migratory species caused by climate change. In this way, they can minimize bird collisions for the next few years. Furthermore, similar models can analyze land (onshore sites), water, vegetation, and other local species in the survey area for determining the optimum construction design that minimizes the impact on ecosystem of the building area. A comparable issue accompanies solar panels with impact on the landscape of installation areas and causing birds to misidentify them as water (Shah et al., 2024). Similarly, these impacts can be predicted by machine learning models during surveys and planning, similar to wind turbine projects.

Achieving accuracy and reliability in artificial intelligence models can only be possible with high-quality and inclusive data. Data integration, organization, quality assurance, and standardizing species data classification are the ideal solutions to the current scattered databases. Data security is another issue that puts the life of animals and conservationists at risk. It is crucial that intergovernmental organizations work with research institutes, scientists, and technology experts to set data protection measures in place to prevent poachers' access to wildlife and conservation data, particularly endangered species. However, they must prevent the influence of governments and corporations in their policymaking to maintain fair data-access for scientists and conservationists in all countries.

Reaching ethical artificial intelligence is crucial in achieving appropriate artificial intelligence-based wildlife conservation strategies. While a number of studies focused on ethical issues in certain regions, their results and suggestions can be applied globally. Researchers that investigate this topic in countries with the largest wildlife habitats and limited conservation and protection resources, can provide real-life evidence for intergovernmental organizations. This information offers insights on how to engage scientists, conservation specialists, and artificial intelligence experts in policymaking, and establishing a wildlife-specific code of ethics and frameworks to tackle ethical issues. Moreover, these organizations must force local governments to align and update their policies with such frameworks. Algorithm audit, fair access to artificial intelligence, data quality and transparency, and wildlife data protection are some

of the solutions recommended by field experts (Galaz et al., 2021; Nandutu et al., 2021; Tuia et al., 2022; De Wilde et al., 2024).

These recommendations are a few actionable steps that can expand the role of artificial intelligence in climate change mitigation and wildlife conservation. Development of machine learning models can establish effective collaboration between technologists, scientists, conservationists, and decision-makers. As efforts to reduce the impacts of climate change on wildlife continue, responsible artificial intelligence solutions can provide reliable, real-time insight and predictive measures to improve these actions. However, this new intelligent companion of wildlife requires appropriate data, and technical and ethical improvements to deeply understand nature and play its role in this crucial state of the planet Earth.

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7. Appendix A

References for renowned machine learning models.

Model Name	Reference
k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN)	Fix, E., Jr. Hodges, J., & University of California, Berkeley. (1951). DISCRIMINATORY ANALYSIS [Report]. https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADA800276.pdf
SVM (Support Vector Machine)	Cortes, C., & Vapnik, V. (1995). Support-vector networks. <i>Machine Learning</i> , 20(3), 273–297. https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00994018
Random Forest	Breiman, L. (2001). Random Forests. <i>Machine Learning</i> , 45(1), 5–32. https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1010933404324
MaxEnt (Maximum Entropy)	Phillips, S. J., Dudík, M., & Schapire, R. E. (2004). A maximum entropy approach to species distribution modeling. <i>Proceedings of the Twenty-First International Conference on Machine Learning</i> . https://doi.org/10.1145/1015330.1015412
AlexNet	Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., & Hinton, G. E. (2017). ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. <i>Communications of the ACM</i> , 60(6), 84–90. https://doi.org/10.1145/3065386
VGG	Simonyan, K., & Zisserman, A. (2014). Very deep convolutional networks for Large-Scale image recognition. <i>arXiv (Cornell University)</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1409.1556
Inception-V3	Szegedy, C., Vanhoucke, V., Ioffe, S., Shlens, J., & Wojna, Z. (2015). Rethinking the inception architecture for computer vision. <i>arXiv (Cornell University)</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1512.00567
ResNet	He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., & Sun, J. (2015). Deep residual learning for image recognition. <i>arXiv (Cornell University)</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1512.03385
YOLO	Redmon, R., Divvala, D., Girshick, G., & Farhadi, F. (2015). You only look once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection. <i>arXiv (Cornell University)</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1506.02640
SqueezeNet	Iandola, F. N., Han, S., Moskewicz, M. W., Ashraf, K., Dally, W. J., & Keutzer, K. (2016). SqueezeNet: AlexNet-level accuracy with 50x fewer parameters and <0.5MB model size. <i>arXiv (Cornell University)</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1602.07360
XGBoost	Chen, T., & Guestrin, C. (2016). XGBoost. <i>Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining</i> , 785–794. https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939785
DenseNet	Huang, G., Liu, Z., Van Der Maaten, L., & Weinberger, K. Q. (2016). Densely connected convolutional networks. <i>arXiv (Cornell University)</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1608.06993
Xception	Chollet, F. (2016). Xception: Deep Learning with Depthwise Separable Convolutions. <i>arXiv (Cornell University)</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1610.02357
LightGBM	Ke, G., Meng, Q., Finely, T., Wang, T., Chen, W., Ma, W., Ye, Q., & Liu, T. (2017). LightGBM: a highly efficient gradient boosting decision Tree - Microsoft Research. <i>Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems</i> , 3149–3157. https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.5555/3294996.3295074
EfficientNet	Tan, M., & Le, Q. V. (2019). EfficientNet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks. <i>arXiv (Cornell University)</i> . https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1905.11946

